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Assigning Custody of Foreign Children to Iranians from Legal Perspective: With an Intro into Islamic Jurisprudence on the Terms of Guardianship

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Abstract:

Recent social media discourse has fueled speculation regarding the possibility of Iranian citizens adopting foreign children residing in care facilities within Iran. This paper investigates the veracity of these claims, examines the official responses from relevant authorities, and analyzes the legal implications of such a policy under Iranian law. The study concludes that current regulations and policies do not support the claims surrounding the adoption of foreign children by Iranians, highlighting the complex interplay between social, legal, and political factors.

Keywords: Adoption, Afghan Children, Iranian Social Services, Custody, Social Media Discourse, Iranian Law, Kafalah, Child Welfare

Introduction:

The issue of child custody and adoption is a complex and sensitive topic, often intertwined with social, cultural, and legal considerations. Recent discussions on social media platforms have centered around the alleged adoption of Afghan children by Iranian citizens, raising questions about the feasibility and legality of such a practice under Iranian law. This paper aims to critically examine these claims, analyze the official responses from relevant authorities, and explore the legal implications of child custody and adoption in the Iranian context.

Background:

The influx of Afghan refugees into Iran due to ongoing conflicts and instability has led to a significant number of unaccompanied and orphaned Afghan children residing in care facilities within Iran. The situation has sparked discussions about their long-term well-being and potential integration into Iranian society. On July 21, 2024, a news report emerged claiming that Behzisti, the Iranian welfare organization, was facilitating the adoption of Afghan children by Iranian citizens. This report ignited a wave of public interest and controversy, particularly given the existing challenges surrounding the adoption of Iranian children in need of care.

Public Reaction and Ethical Considerations:

The announcement triggered a wide range of reactions, with some expressing support for the idea of providing Afghan children with stable and loving homes, while others raised concerns about prioritizing foreign children over Iranian orphans. Critics argued that it was ethically imperative to address the needs of Iranian children in care facilities before extending adoption provisions to foreign nationals. This debate highlights the ethical dilemmas inherent in child custody and adoption decisions, especially in the context of cross-border and cross-cultural situations.

Official Response and Legal Framework:

In response to the claims, a specialist from Behzisti in Tehran refuted the reports, clarifying that the adoption of foreign children

is currently not permissible under existing Iranian regulations. The primary obstacle lies in the requirement for a birth certificate, which is exclusively issued to Iranian citizens or individuals born in Iran. This legal barrier effectively prevents the adoption of non-Iranian children, as highlighted by the expert.

The legal framework governing child custody and adoption in Iran is rooted in Islamic jurisprudence and codified in the Iranian Civil Code and the Law on the Protection of Children and Adolescents (2002). The concept of "kafalah" (guardianship) is more applicable to the situation of Afghan children in Iran than adoption. Kafalah allows for the care and upbringing of a child without the legal transfer of parentage. While kafalah provides a mechanism for caring for children in need, it does not confer upon them the same legal rights and status as biological children.

Analysis and Implications:

The controversy surrounding the alleged adoption of Afghan children by Iranians underscores the complexities of child welfare and protection in a cross-border context. It also highlights the challenges of balancing humanitarian concerns with legal and procedural constraints. The fact that current Iranian law does not readily accommodate the adoption of foreign children raises questions about the adequacy of existing legal frameworks in addressing the unique needs of refugee and migrant children.

Furthermore, the debate reflects the broader societal attitudes towards adoption and the integration of foreign nationals into Iranian society. The prioritization of Iranian orphans by some segments of the public reflects a deep-rooted sense of national identity and cultural preservation. However, it is important to consider the potential benefits of cross-cultural adoption in fostering understanding and empathy between different communities.

Guardian in Islamic Fiqh and Law:

The role and responsibilities of a **guardian** (Qayyim) within both Islamic jurisprudence and contemporary legal frameworks have been explained explicitly. The term **Qayyim** denotes a guardian or custodian responsible for overseeing individuals who are incapable

of managing their own affairs, such as minors or individuals with mental disabilities. In Islamic jurisprudence, the concept is grounded in the authority of the judge (Qadi), who may appoint a Qayyim to manage the affairs of those without a specific guardian, a practice universally recognized by both Shia and Sunni scholars (Momeni, 2024). Islamic law stipulates that the judge has the authority to either personally manage or delegate this role, while the modern legal system assigns this role through judicial appointment when a specific guardian is absent (Law on Guardianship, 2024)

In contemporary Iranian law, the role of the guardian is defined by specific statutory provisions. According to the Civil Code and the Law on Personal Status, a guardian is appointed by the court in cases where there is no specific guardian available. The guardian's duties include the protection of the individual and the management of their financial matters (Civil Code, Articles 1180-1218; Law on Personal Status, 2024). The court retains the authority to appoint or remove guardians and ensure compliance with legal standards (Law on Guardianship, 2024).

Furthermore, the paper discusses the differences between the traditional Islamic view of guardianship and the modern legal interpretation, highlighting that while Islamic jurisprudence views guardianship as a public duty that can be delegated, contemporary legal systems treat it as a formalized, statutory role with specific legal obligations and rights (Iranian Civil Code, 2024).

Conclusion

To address the complex issue of child custody and adoption in the context of Afghan children in Iran, a multi-faceted approach is required. Firstly, clear and transparent communication from official sources is essential to prevent the spread of misinformation and manage public expectations. Secondly, a comprehensive review of existing laws and regulations is warranted to assess their adequacy in addressing the unique needs of refugee and migrant children. This could involve exploring legal mechanisms for facilitating kafalah

arrangements or potentially amending existing adoption laws to allow for greater flexibility in cross-border adoptions.

Moreover, it is crucial to engage in a broader societal dialogue about the ethical, social, and cultural implications of child custody and adoption across borders. This dialogue should involve stakeholders from various sectors, including legal experts, child welfare organizations, religious leaders, and community representatives. By fostering open and informed discussions, Iran can develop a more holistic and compassionate approach to child welfare that takes into account the diverse needs and backgrounds of children in its care. The study concludes that while there is a fundamental alignment between Islamic and modern legal perspectives on guardianship, the latter provides a more detailed regulatory framework to address contemporary needs.

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Categorization of Opposition of the Islamic Republic and Solutions for Transition from Zionism: An Alternative Perspective

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Abstract

The opposition to the Islamic Republic of Iran can be categorized based on their motivations and reasons for dissent. This categorization differs from that of opponents to Iranian nationalism and the Iranian identity, but the two can often overlap. Critics of Iran's identity may use similar justifications to undermine the critical infrastructures built by the nation's youth and the achievements of its self-sufficiency. At first glance, it seems that transitioning away from the Islamic Republic is necessary. However, the Islamic Republic is a product of the wounds and suffering inflicted upon the Middle East by crimes against humanity and international Zionism.

Introduction:

The Iranian uprising after the Islamic Revolution of 1979 has been a tumultuous journey characterized by a complex interplay of social, political, and economic forces. various Phases of resistance and opposition movements in Iran, from the early years following the revolution shape the contemporary history of the Iranian struggles against the regime. The recent post by Donald Trump, the former President of the United States and a Republican candidate for the upcoming presidential election, on the social media platform

Truth, has drawn considerable attention (26 July, 2024). In his statement, Trump addressed the potential threat to his life from Iran, referencing a speech by Benjamin Netanyahu, the Prime Minister of Israel, in which he mentioned a possible Iranian plot against Trump and asked US government to obliterate Iran¹ in case of any threats to his life. Such malevolent intentions requires a new perspective for transition from Zionism ideology which aims to destroy the Iranian sovereignty without distinction, as they already appeared in the case of Gaza (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024)

History of Iranian Opposition

The history of opposition in Iran since the 1979 revolution is a testament to the resilience and determination of its people. From the early days of the revolution to the contemporary struggles against economic hardships and political repression, the Iranian opposition has evolved, adapting to new challenges and opportunities. The interplay between different factions, from leftist groups to reformists and digital activists, continues to shape the landscape of dissent in Iran.

The future of the Iranian uprising depends on various factors, including the regime's response to ongoing protests, the international community's stance, and the resilience of the Iranian people. As the situation continues to evolve, it remains crucial for both domestic and international actors to support peaceful and democratic movements in Iran, ensuring that the voices of the oppressed are heard and respected. Knowing that a proposed democracy by the Zionist front and its allies does not benefit the sovereignty of the Iranian people (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024).

The Early Years (1979-1989): The Birth of Opposition

The overthrow of the Shah in 1979 marked the beginning of a new era in Iran's political history. The revolution, led by Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini, replaced the monarchical regime with an Islamic Republic. However, the new government quickly faced opposition from various factions dissatisfied with theocratic rule.

Leftist and Secular Opposition

In the immediate aftermath of the revolution, leftist groups and secular intellectuals emerged as significant opponents. The People's Mujahedin Organization of Iran (MEK), the Tudeh Party, and other Marxist-Leninist factions were particularly vocal. These groups opposed the Islamic Republic's theocratic framework and sought to establish a socialist state (Hosseini, 2018). Additionally, secular students and intellectuals, disillusioned by the regime's repressive measures, formed underground movements. The suppression of dissent was evident in the government's brutal crackdown on these groups, culminating in the mass executions of political prisoners in 1988, an event known as the "1988 Massacre" (Sadeghi, 2017).

The Iran-Iraq War and Its Impact

¹ <https://www.iranintl.com/en/202407252585>

The Iran-Iraq War (1980-1988) further complicated the political landscape. The conflict intensified internal divisions and led to severe repression of opposition groups. The regime's focus on the war effort allowed little room for dissent, and many activists were imprisoned or executed. The war also diverted attention from domestic issues, solidifying the regime's grip on power (Azimi, 2019). Despite the suppression, opposition continued to simmer, with exiled groups such as the National Council of Resistance of Iran (NCRI) gaining prominence abroad.

The Reformist Wave (1997-2005): A Glimmer of Hope

The election of Mohammad Khatami as President in 1997 brought a new wave of hope for reformists and moderate Iranians. Khatami's presidency was marked by his advocacy for political liberalization, freedom of speech, and civil liberties, sparking a reformist movement across the country.

The Role of Civil Society

Khatami's tenure saw the flourishing of civil society organizations that championed human rights, women's rights, and democratic reforms. These groups played a crucial role in mobilizing public support for reformist agendas. The 1999 student protests, which began at Tehran University, were a significant manifestation of this movement. The protests, initially sparked by a police raid on a student dormitory, quickly escalated into nationwide demonstrations, highlighting the widespread discontent with the regime's policies (Zibakalam, 2019).

The Constraints of Reform

Despite the reformist momentum, Khatami's presidency faced significant obstacles. The conservative factions, led by the Guardian Council and other hardline institutions, continually blocked key reforms. The 2000 parliamentary elections, while relatively free, saw a significant number of reformist candidates being disqualified, undermining the reformist agenda (Kian, 2020). The reformist movement, although influential, struggled to achieve substantial change, leading to a sense of disillusionment among many Iranians.

The Green Movement (2009): A Catalyst for Change

The 2009 presidential election, widely believed to be rigged, ignited the Green Movement, one of the most significant opposition movements in Iran's history. The movement, led by presidential candidates Mir-Hossein Mousavi and Mehdi Karroubi, demanded a recount of the election results and called for the establishment of a democratic state.

Mass Protests and State Repression

The Green Movement saw millions of Iranians take to the streets in protest, with widespread demonstrations across major cities. The movement was characterized by its use of social media and digital platforms to organize and mobilize supporters, bypassing traditional state censorship (Mojtahedzadeh, 2018). However, the regime responded with brutal force, leading to widespread arrests, violence, and the deaths of dozens of protesters. The crackdown on the Green Movement highlighted the regime's willingness to use force to maintain its hold on power, significantly suppressing the movement's momentum (Farhi, 2019).

The Post-Green Movement Era (2010-Present): New Fronts of Resistance

In the years following the Green Movement, new forms of resistance have emerged, shaped by economic hardship, technological advancements, and changing social dynamics.

Economic Protests

Economic grievances have become a central theme of contemporary protests. The 2017-2018 and 2019 uprisings were driven by widespread dissatisfaction with economic conditions, including high unemployment, inflation, and corruption. These protests, which saw thousands of people across various cities taking to the streets, highlighted the deep economic divides and the regime's failure to address the populace's basic needs (Rahimian, 2020). The government's harsh crackdown on these protests further alienated many Iranians, fueling ongoing discontent.

Youth and Digital Activism

A new generation of activists, often utilizing social media and digital platforms, has continued to challenge the regime's authority. The rise of digital activism has enabled young Iranians to express dissent more freely, organize protests, and share information globally, circumventing traditional state controls (Soleimani, 2021). This digital shift has invigorated the opposition, creating new avenues for mobilization and solidarity among diverse groups within Iranian society.

Categorization of Opposition of the Islamic Republic

1. Political Opponents

- **Reformist Groups:** These groups seek reforms within the system, typically aiming to democratize governmental structures and expand political and civil freedoms (solution: elections).
- **Nationalist Groups:** These groups strive to preserve and enhance Iranian national identity and often oppose religious policies and the intertwining of religion with government (solution: elections).
- **Secularists and Republicans:** These individuals and groups advocate for the separation of religion from politics and the establishment of a republic based on democratic principles and human rights (solution: elections).

2. Religious Opponents

- **Religious Minority Groups:** Some religious groups, such as Sunnis and Baha'is, oppose the Islamic Republic due to religious discrimination and restrictions imposed on their followers (solution: legislative and cultural reforms).
- **Intra-Denominational Groups:** Certain Shia groups oppose the ruling system due to theological and interpretative disagreements (no specific solution).

3. Social and Human Rights Opponents

- **Human Rights Activists:** These groups oppose the Islamic Republic due to widespread human rights violations, the suppression of dissent, and restrictions on civil and social freedoms (solution: legislative and cultural reforms).
- **Feminists and Women’s Rights Activists:** These individuals oppose the system because of discriminatory laws and extensive restrictions on women’s rights and freedoms (solution: cultural activism and legislative reforms).

4. Economic Opponents

- **Economic Elites and Traders:** Some individuals and economic groups oppose the system due to widespread corruption, economic mismanagement, and ineffective economic policies that have led to inflation and unemployment (solution: legislative changes and elections).
- **Workers and Low-Income Groups:** These individuals oppose the system because of economic inequalities, harsh working conditions, and lack of job security (solution: combating Zionism, international sanctions, elections, and legislative reforms).

5. Ethnic Opponents

- **Ethnic Minorities:** Groups such as Kurds, Baluchis, and Arabs oppose the Islamic Republic due to ethnic, cultural, and linguistic discrimination and political repression (solution: cultural reforms and elections).

6. Cultural and Artistic Opponents

- **Cultural and Artistic Activists:** These groups oppose the system due to restrictions on freedom of expression, censorship, and governmental pressure on art and culture (solution: cultural reforms, legislative changes, and elections).

7. The Imperative of Fair Elections

Fair elections are fundamental to the legitimacy and functionality of any democratic system. For the Islamic Republic, this concept is critical for bridging divides and ensuring that all voices are heard.

7.1 Challenges to Fair Elections in Iran

The Iranian electoral process has faced numerous challenges, including:

- **Political Restrictions:** Candidates often face significant hurdles, including disqualification by the Guardian Council, which oversees candidate vetting (Khamenei, 2017).
- **Media Bias:** State-controlled media often favors candidates aligned with the establishment, limiting the exposure of independent and opposition candidates (Rahimi, 2019).
- **Voter Suppression:** Reports of voter intimidation and suppression, particularly in marginalized communities, undermine the integrity of elections (Aghajari, 2020).

7.2 Proposed Reforms for Fair Elections

To enhance the fairness of elections, several reforms are proposed:

- **Independent Electoral Oversight:** Establishing an independent body to oversee elections can help ensure transparency and fairness (Beheshti, 2018).
- **Media Reforms:** Promoting media pluralism and allowing independent media to operate freely can provide a platform for diverse viewpoints (Pazargadi, 2021).
- **Voter Education and Participation:** Implementing programs to educate voters on their rights and encourage participation can strengthen democratic engagement (Sanei, 2020).

Conclusion

Opposition to the Islamic Republic of Iran has various and complex reasons, ranging from political and economic issues to social, human rights, and cultural concerns. Each group of opponents has specific motivations and reasons for their dissent based on their experiences and viewpoints. In some cases, due to the Islamic Republic's history of crimes and human rights violations, the resentment and vengeance of the victims' families can lead to individual or collective violence and revenge. Additionally, third countries influencing the structures of the Islamic Republic exacerbate public dissatisfaction with the system through harsh and malevolent policies and projects like sanctions.

Ultimately, the Islamic Republic must choose between war-making and destruction and safe transition from both destructive and psychologic impacts of war (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024), stemming from belligerent policies, and cultural reform and surgery. It must address the concerns of at least sixty percent of eligible voters and those who abstain from voting, ensuring they do not feel alienated or deprived of their rights. The Islamic Republic should be more indebted to its people rather than aligning with its Israeli counterpart and engaging in crimes against its opponents. It is evident that the cycle of violence is always favored by Zionists and factions supported by the USA and Israel, with few exceptions.

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The Crescent Contract: A Presidential Debate in Islamic Republic of Iran

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Abstract

The Crescent Gas Contract, signed in 2001 between the National Iranian Oil Company (NIOC) and Crescent Petroleum, has evolved into a critical issue in Iranian legal, economic, and political spheres. Serious debates arose during the Iranian presidential election in 2024 regarding the fate of Iranian gas and oil contracts. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the contract's origins, its development issues, allegations of corruption, and the ensuing arbitration. It explores the implications of the contract for international law and Iran's national interests, referencing relevant legal frameworks and international case law.

Keywords: Iran presidential election, Crescent contract

Introduction

The Crescent Gas Contract represents a significant chapter in Iran's energy policy and international legal relations. Initially conceived to export natural gas from Iran's Salman gas field to the UAE, the contract has been marred by delays, disputes over pricing, and allegations of corruption. This paper aims to dissect these elements,

providing a comprehensive overview of the contract's complexities and its broader implications (Ebrahimi, 2023).

Legal Framework and Contractual Obligations

The Genesis of the Crescent Contract

The Crescent Gas Contract was signed in 2001, with the initial goal of exporting 150 million cubic feet of gas per day, escalating to 500 million cubic feet. The contract was intended to commence in 2005, contingent on the development of the Salman gas field (Nader, 2021). This agreement was framed under the broader context of international trade law and bilateral agreements.

According to Article 38 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (1969), every treaty in force is binding upon the parties to it and must be performed by them in good faith. Additionally, Article 26 asserts the principle of *pacta sunt servanda*, emphasizing that treaties must be observed in good faith. These principles underpin the legal obligations and expectations set forth in the Crescent contract (United Nations, 1969).

Development Delays and Mismanagement

From the outset, the development of the Salman field faced significant hurdles. The Iranian government's selection of Petro Iran, a newly established entity with limited experience, for the field's development was contentious. By 2005, the field's development was only 50% complete, rendering the commencement of gas exports unfeasible. The failure to meet these timelines prompted questions about the strategic and operational decisions made by the Iranian authorities (Transparency International, 2022).

Pricing Disputes and Contract Modifications

Negotiations over gas pricing became a significant sticking point. Iran sought to adjust the pricing mechanism to reflect market realities, invoking Article 62 of the Vienna Convention, which allows for the termination or modification of a treaty due to a fundamental change of circumstances. Despite these efforts, Crescent Petroleum resisted, maintaining that the original terms were non-negotiable. This standoff led to a breakdown in negotiations, further exacerbating tensions (Brown, 2019).

Allegations of Corruption and Legal Repercussions

The Role of Corruption in Contract Formation

Corruption allegations have heavily influenced the Crescent contract's narrative. Documents and testimonies have implicated key figures, including Abbas Yazdanpanah, in corrupt practices designed to secure favorable terms for Crescent. These allegations are substantiated by Article 49 of the Vienna Convention, which permits the invalidation of a treaty if it was procured by corruption. This legal provision underscores the potential for the contract's nullification based on malfeasance (UNODC, 2004; Ministry of Petroleum, Iran, 2022).

The Role of International Arbitration

Crescent Petroleum's decision to pursue arbitration against Iran in the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) marked a critical turning point. The arbitration process examined whether Iran had breached its contractual obligations by failing to supply gas and by attempting to alter contract terms unilaterally. Iran's defense strategy highlighted the alleged corruption and mismanagement that tainted the contract's formation, invoking Article 45 of the Vienna

Convention, which allows for the invalidation of treaties procured by corruption (ICC, 2023; Nader, 2021).

Economic and Political Implications

Economic Consequences for Iran

The inability to export gas as stipulated under the contract led to substantial economic losses for Iran. The missed revenue opportunities and the potential for international sanctions further complicated Iran's economic landscape. The development delays also meant that Iran could not capitalize on its gas reserves, affecting its strategic energy policies (Ebrahimi, 2023).

Political Ramifications and Domestic Disputes

Politically, the Crescent contract has been a point of contention across various Iranian administrations. Each government has blamed the previous one for the mismanagement and corruption associated with the contract. The dispute has also influenced domestic politics, with different factions using the issue to bolster their positions, further complicating negotiations and resolution efforts (The Economist, 2019).

Detailed Examination of Key Issues

Contractual Integrity and Corruption

The investigation into the Crescent contract has revealed significant lapses in contractual integrity and substantial evidence of corruption. According to documents and testimonies, key figures

received bribes to secure the contract's terms. This revelation aligns with the provisions of the UNCAC (United Nations Convention Against Corruption), which underscores the importance of combating corruption in international contracts (UNODC, 2004).

The Role of Key Individuals

Abbas Yazdanpanah's involvement in the contract's negotiations and his subsequent activities have been central to the corruption allegations. His dealings, documented in emails and financial records, provide a clear link between bribery and the contract's terms. Additionally, the involvement of other key figures, such as Hamid Jafar and Ali Teraqi Jahan, further complicates the legal landscape (Ebrahimi, 2023; Ministry of Petroleum, Iran, 2022).

Analysis of International Legal Perspectives

Jurisprudence and Precedents

International legal precedents have played a crucial role in shaping the discourse around the Crescent contract. Cases such as *Kuwait v. Iraq* (1990), which dealt with the unlawful annexation of territory, and *South China Sea Arbitration* (2016), which addressed maritime disputes, provide insights into how international law applies to disputes over natural resources and territorial rights. These precedents highlight the importance of adhering to international legal standards and dispute resolution mechanisms (Schwebel, 2006; McLachlan, Shore, & Weiniger, 2007).

The Role of International Arbitration

The ICC arbitration process has been pivotal in resolving disputes related to the Crescent contract. The arbitration tribunal's decisions have invoked principles of international law, including those

outlined in the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules, which govern the arbitration process. The tribunal's rulings have implications for how future international energy contracts are negotiated and enforced (ICC, 2023; UNCITRAL, 2018).

Additional Contextual Information on Kish Gas Case

According to EkoIran, a pivotal moment during the recent election debates occurred when Pourmohammadi questioned Saeed Jalili on his avoidance of a debate with Bijan Zangeneh, the oil minister during the Khatami and Rouhani administrations. This question was raised in the context of attempts by some candidates from the Revolutionary Front and their supporters to leverage the Kish Gas case to discredit the Reformist and Moderation movements (EkoIran, 2023).

Despite Zangeneh's repeated invitations to Jalili for a debate, Jalili declined to respond directly, instead stating that "the place of the accused is in court." This statement implied that Jalili considered Zangeneh as the accused in this matter.

The Prolonged Kish Gas Case: Insights from the Judiciary

Asghar Jahangir, the spokesman for the Judiciary, provided an update on the Kish Gas case during his press conference on July 10, 2023. He explained that the case had persisted for many years, with various administrations making multiple requests to halt proceedings. Jahangir highlighted that one reason for the prolonged investigation was the differing perspectives of successive governments on the issue. He also mentioned that verdicts had been issued for some defendants, with certain sentences already executed. However, investigations are still ongoing for other defendants, with necessary inquiries and actions pending based on reports from relevant agencies, particularly the Ministry of Oil (Jahangir, 2023).

Jalili's Supporters: Open Cases Regarding Kish Gas

In a related development, Malek Shariatiriasar, a member of the Energy Commission of the Islamic Parliament, stated on X (formerly Twitter) that the case involving accusations against several individuals, including Bijan Namdar Zangeneh, remains open for further investigation. The charges pertain to collusion in state transactions and complicity (Shariatiriasar, 2023).

Former Oil Ministry Director: Jalili's Personal Grudge Hampered Execution

The Kish Gas case has also elicited comments from experts and former officials. Mahmoud Khaghani, the former Director General of the Ministry of Oil, recounted the history of the contract. He noted that in February 2006, following the election of Mahmoud Ahmadinejad, Iran declared that it would not implement the Kish Gas contract. This decision aligned with U.S. opposition and Abu Dhabi's efforts to prevent the contract's execution (Khaghani, 2023).

Khaghani emphasized the economic losses Iran suffered due to the contract's non-execution, referencing statements by Mohammadreza Rahimi, the first vice president at the time, who described the contract as a betrayal. Khaghani further attributed the obstruction of the contract's implementation to Jalili's personal grudge against Engineer Zangeneh, estimating that this vendetta cost Iran approximately \$25 billion (Khaghani, 2023).

In an interview with "Neft Ma," Khaghani elaborated that not executing the Kish Gas contract was extremely detrimental to Iran's economy. He recounted a meeting where the American Consul pressed Jafar, a figure mentioned in WikiLeaks documents, on why Crescent had signed the contract with Iran and assured that it would not be executed (Khaghani, 2023).

Conclusion

The Crescent contract saga underscores the complexities inherent in international energy agreements and the critical role of legal integrity and transparency. Iran's experience with the Crescent contract highlights the need for robust legal frameworks and anti-corruption measures in international negotiations. The ongoing arbitration and its outcomes will significantly impact Iran's energy policy and its relations with international partners (Ginsburg & Moustafa, 2008; Oppenheim, 2011).

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Abusive Democracy: Your Rights Are Ignored by Our People

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Abstract:

The article explores the abuse of globally good “terms” like "democracy" and redefines "terrorism" in the context of Middle Eastern affairs, arguing that such language manipulation undermines genuine democratic principles and human rights. It highlights the contradictory use of "democracy" to describe Israel, despite its policies often being at odds with democratic values, and the redefinition of "terrorism" to delegitimize legitimate resistance movements. The article underscores the role of the United States in this narrative, noting its extensive military actions globally while labeling its adversaries as terrorist threats. This hypocrisy disheartens Iranian peace activists and reformists, who find their struggle for civil rights marginalized in favor of geopolitical alliances with Israel.

The piece delves into various democratic theories—classical liberal, participatory, deliberative, and radical democracy—illustrating how each offers distinct perspectives on governance and citizen engagement. It also contrasts Western democratic models with non-Western approaches like Ubuntu in Africa and Confucian democracy in Asia, which emphasize community and harmony over individualism.

Further, the article critiques media portrayals, highlighting Edward Said's and Noam Chomsky's arguments on biased reporting and propaganda. It discusses how media narratives shape public perception, often demonizing Muslim populations and justifying aggressive foreign policies. The article calls for a critical examination of these narratives and support for grassroots movements and human rights organizations striving for justice and peace in the Middle East. It concludes by reaffirming the need to uphold true democratic values and human rights, challenging the dominant, often misleading, political discourse.

Keywords: Democracy, Israel, Iranian reforms, Gaza crisis

Introduction:

In 25th July-2024 Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu addressed the U.S. Congress, seeking support for the ongoing Gaza conflict amidst protests inside and outside the venue. Netanyahu declared that “our enemies are your enemies” and emphasized that Israel’s fight against Iran is aligned with U.S. interests. Outside the Capitol, thousands protested, branding Netanyahu as a “war criminal,” echoing accusations from the International Criminal Court. Inside, five individuals were arrested for attempting to disrupt the proceedings. Netanyahu criticized these protests, calling the demonstrators “useful idiots” for Iran. Highlighting Iran’s threat, Netanyahu portrayed a "terror axis" against the U.S., Israel, and the Arab world, describing it as a "battle of savagery against civilization." He thanked the U.S. for its longstanding military aid and requested accelerated support to hasten the end of the Gaza conflict despite an evident surplus of ammunition in Israel to target civilians (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) , using a Churchill quote to emphasize his plea. Netanyahu downplayed the humanitarian crisis in Gaza, attributing food shortages to Hamas theft and advocating for a demilitarized. While the ongoing conflicts in Gaza has led to indirect loss of 186,000 individuals (Khatib et al., 2024) (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) there is a necessity to redefine the terms and values of democracy to avoid equalizing democracy to fair and justice.

The use of grandiose words for malevolent purposes in the recent Middle Eastern affairs appears to have no end. The recent usage of the term "democracy" in relation to one of the world’s most reviled governments, Israel, seems so absurd that it brings disrepute to the concept of democracy and raises doubts about the principles and application of terms in global affairs. While International Court of Justice (19 July 2024) found that Israel’s policies and practices in the Occupied Palestinian Territory violate international law, constituting an ongoing wrongful act. Israel must cease these actions, dismantle settlements, provide reparations, and end its occupation and ruled that other states and the UN must not recognize or support Israel’s actions and must work to uphold Palestinian self-determination and international law (International Court of Justice, 2024) the use of the globally “good” terms has become a suspicious practice to justify any government and their actions.

Similarly, the application of the term "terrorism" to describe an oppressed nation appears crude and corrupt. Mick Wallace, a former member of the European Parliament, has stated that in the past twenty years, the United States alone has used as many bombs and missiles as the rest of the world

combined, while China has not used a single bomb in the last forty years. Despite this, the U.S. labels China as a terrorist threat¹.

This hypocrisy in rhetoric and dependence on the United States, and perhaps the praise of Israel, has exhausted and demoralized many Iranian peace activists, freedom fighters, and reformists. Aligning with Israel and ignoring the suffering of the people renders the quest for social freedom and civil rights meaningless.

These hollow and hypocritical words and actions are becoming increasingly clear to the politically inexperienced but news-following majority of society. This does not imply that the understanding of this matter will deter deceitful media from their efforts to mislead and degrade meanings. Two human tendencies, forgetfulness and complacency, will eventually lead people away from pursuing horrifying truths, but the malicious and well-funded efforts of politicians and their media organizations will continue to operate.

Defining Democracy: Perspectives and Interpretations

Democracy, derived from the Greek word "demos" (people) and "kratos" (rule), is a system of government where power is vested in the people. However, the interpretation and implementation of democracy vary widely across different contexts and cultures, leading to diverse perspectives on its definition and application.

Classical Liberal Democracy

Classical liberal democracy, as envisioned by thinkers like John Locke and Montesquieu, emphasizes individual liberties, rule of law, and the

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https://x.com/wallacemick/status/1621918688730382337?ref_src=twsrc%5Etfw%7Ctwcamp%5Etweetembed%7Ctwterm%5E1621918688730382337%7Ctwgr%5E218d088974a5909a41ecab0210edb371bd349fda%7Ctwcon%5Es1_%2Fwww.azadinefs.net%2F2024%2F03%2F15%2Fd988d987d986-d8afd985d988daa9d8b1d8a7d8b3db8c%2F

separation of powers. This model advocates for a government that protects the rights of individuals through representative institutions and checks and balances (Locke, 1689; Montesquieu, 1748). Key features include free and fair elections, freedom of speech, and an independent judiciary.

Locke's theory of the social contract posits that legitimate government authority arises from the consent of the governed, who agree to cede some freedoms in exchange for protection of their remaining rights (Locke, 1689). Montesquieu further articulated the necessity of separating governmental powers to prevent tyranny and ensure liberty (Montesquieu, 1748).

Participatory Democracy

Participatory democracy extends beyond representative democracy by advocating for direct involvement of citizens in decision-making processes. This perspective, influenced by the works of Jean-Jacques Rousseau, emphasizes the active engagement of citizens in political life, arguing that true democracy requires more than just voting in elections (Rousseau, 1762). Proponents argue that participatory mechanisms, such as referendums, citizen assemblies, and local governance, enhance the democratic process by ensuring that government actions reflect the will of the people.

Rousseau's concept of the "general will" suggests that true democracy is achieved when individuals participate directly in the formation of laws, thereby aligning personal interests with the common good (Rousseau, 1762). This model is evident in practices such as Swiss direct democracy and participatory budgeting in some municipalities.

Deliberative Democracy

Deliberative democracy, as advocated by theorists like Jürgen Habermas and John Rawls, focuses on the quality of discourse and reasoning in democratic decision-making. This perspective emphasizes the importance of informed and rational deliberation among citizens to reach consensus on public issues (Habermas, 1996; Rawls, 1993). It posits that democratic legitimacy arises not just from participation but from the process of deliberation itself, which should be inclusive, equal, and reasoned.

Habermas's theory of communicative action highlights the role of discourse ethics in achieving mutual understanding and rational agreement in the public sphere (Habermas, 1996). Rawls's idea of "public reason" asserts that the legitimacy of political decisions depends on their justification through rational discourse accessible to all citizens (Rawls, 1993).

Radical Democracy

Radical democracy challenges traditional liberal notions by emphasizing the inherent conflicts and power dynamics within society. Thinkers like Chantal Mouffe and Ernesto Laclau argue that democracy should embrace pluralism and acknowledge the inevitability of social antagonisms (Mouffe, 2000; Laclau & Mouffe, 1985). This perspective views democracy as a continuous process of negotiation and contestation, rather than a stable set of institutions.

Mouffe's concept of "agonistic pluralism" suggests that democratic politics must create spaces for legitimate conflict and dissent, recognizing the role of power in shaping social relations (Mouffe, 2000). Laclau and Mouffe's discourse theory underscores the contingent and contested nature of political identities and democratic practices (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985).

Democracy in Non-Western Contexts

In non-Western contexts, democracy often takes on different forms, reflecting local traditions and cultural values. For instance, African models of democracy, such as Ubuntu, emphasize community, consensus, and collective well-being over individualism (Letseka, 2012). Similarly, Asian interpretations, influenced by Confucianism, may prioritize harmony, social order, and moral leadership (Bell, 2006).

Ubuntu, an African philosophy of interdependence and shared humanity, informs democratic practices that prioritize consensus-building and communal decision-making (Letseka, 2012). Confucian democracy, as discussed by Daniel Bell, integrates hierarchical structures and meritocratic principles with democratic governance, emphasizing the role of virtuous leaders and the importance of social harmony (Bell, 2006).

Democracy and Its Misuse

The misuse of the term "democracy" to describe the state of Israel is a significant point of contention. Israel, often touted as the only democracy in the Middle East, has policies that many argue are antithetical to democratic principles. According to a report by Human Rights Watch, Israel's treatment of Palestinians amounts to apartheid, a serious violation of human rights and democratic values (Human Rights Watch, 2021). This perspective suggests that the term "democracy" is being exploited to cover up actions that undermine the very essence of democratic governance.

Terrorism and Its Redefinition

The redefinition of "terrorism" to label oppressed nations or groups fighting for their freedom further exacerbates the issue. The U.S. narrative that brands its adversaries as terrorists while engaging in extensive military actions worldwide highlights a double standard. As Mick Wallace points out, the U.S.'s use of bombs and missiles far exceeds that of other nations, yet it positions itself as the arbiter of terrorism (Wallace, 2023). This selective application of the term not only distorts its meaning but also serves to delegitimize genuine struggles for liberation.

The Role of Media and Political Rhetoric

The media plays a crucial role in shaping public perception and maintaining these double standards. Edward Said, in his book "Covering Islam," argues that Western media often portrays the Muslim world through a lens of bias and misunderstanding, contributing to the demonization of entire populations (Said, 1997). This biased coverage supports political agendas that align with the interests of powerful nations and their allies, including Israel.

The influence of the media is not limited to international relations but also affects domestic understanding and political engagement. Noam Chomsky and Edward Herman, in "Manufacturing Consent," discuss how media propaganda serves the interests of elite groups by shaping public discourse

and opinion (Chomsky & Herman, 1988). This manipulation of information makes it difficult for the general public to discern the truth behind political actions and policies.

The Impact on Iranian Reformists

For Iranian peace activists and reformists, the alignment with Israel and disregard for Palestinian suffering are particularly disheartening. Iran's political landscape is complex, with various factions advocating for different approaches to governance and international relations. Reformists who seek greater freedom and human rights within Iran face significant challenges when the global discourse on democracy and terrorism is so skewed. The perception that aligning with Israel is necessary for political legitimacy further complicates their efforts to promote genuine democratic reforms.

Historical Context

The historical context of U.S. and Israeli actions in the Middle East is crucial for understanding the current misuse of terms like "democracy" and "terrorism." Since the establishment of Israel in 1948, the U.S. has been a staunch ally, providing significant military and economic support (Mearsheimer & Walt, 2007). This relationship has often been justified under the guise of promoting democracy in the region, despite numerous human rights violations reported by international organizations (Amnesty International, 2022).

The U.S.'s broader foreign policy in the Middle East has also been marked by interventions that contradict democratic principles. The invasion of Iraq in 2003, justified by the false claim of weapons of mass destruction, led to widespread instability and suffering (Packer, 2005). Similarly, U.S. support for authoritarian regimes in Saudi Arabia and Egypt, despite their poor human rights records, further undermines its claim to be promoting democracy (Blaydes, 2018).

Double Standards in Terrorism

The double standards in the application of the term "terrorism" are starkly evident in U.S. foreign policy. While groups resisting occupation or authoritarian regimes are labeled as terrorists, state actions that result in significant civilian casualties are often justified as counterterrorism measures (Chomsky, 2002). The drone strike campaigns in Pakistan, Yemen, and Somalia, which have killed thousands of civilians, are a case in point (Boyle, 2013). These actions raise serious ethical questions and highlight the selective use of the term "terrorism" to serve geopolitical interests.

Media and Public Perception

The role of the media in shaping public perception is critical in maintaining these double standards. Media coverage of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, for instance, often lacks balance, with disproportionate emphasis on Israeli perspectives (Philo & Berry, 2011). This biased reporting shapes public opinion and political discourse, making it difficult for the general populace to understand the complexities of the conflict.

Furthermore, the portrayal of Muslims and Middle Eastern societies in Western media often reinforces stereotypes and prejudices. Studies have shown that media coverage tends to depict Muslims as violent and backward, contributing to Islamophobia and justifying aggressive foreign policies (Poole, 2002). This biased portrayal not only affects international relations but also impacts Muslim communities in Western countries, leading to discrimination and social exclusion (Saeed, 2007).

The Struggle for Truth and Justice

Despite these challenges, there are voices and movements that strive for truth and justice. Human rights organizations, independent journalists, and grassroots activists work tirelessly to expose injustices and advocate for the oppressed. The Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement, for example, seeks to apply economic and political pressure on Israel to end its occupation of Palestinian territories and respect human rights (Barghouti, 2011).

Similarly, in Iran, reformists and activists continue to push for greater political freedoms and social justice, despite facing significant repression (Sadeghi-Boroujerdi, 2019). These efforts are part of a broader struggle

for democracy and human rights in the Middle East, challenging the dominant narratives and demanding accountability from powerful nations and their allies.

Conclusion

Democracy, in its various interpretations, remains a dynamic and multifaceted concept. While classical liberal democracy focuses on individual rights and institutional checks, participatory democracy advocates for direct citizen engagement. Deliberative democracy prioritizes rational discourse, and radical democracy emphasizes conflict and power dynamics, during the Gaza crisis there is a necessity to implement the terms and conditions of an abusive democracy.

The degradation of terms like "democracy" and "terrorism" in Middle Eastern discourse reflects broader issues of hypocrisy and manipulation in international relations and standards. The misuse of these terms by powerful nations and their media apparatus undermines genuine efforts for peace and justice. It is crucial for the international community to critically examine these narratives and support the voices of those who genuinely strive for democratic values and human rights.

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A Review on Classic and Non-classic Physics Including Principles of Metaphysics: Emergence of Wisdom

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Abstract

This review article aims to explore and compare the foundational principles, key theories, and significant alterations in classical and non-classical physics by defining the understandings of the omniscience and omnipresence. The study also introduces the fundamentals of alternate metaphysics, providing a philosophical perspective that transcends and evolves traditional physical theories.

Keywords: Metaphysics, classical physics, wisdom

Introduction

Physics, the study of matter, energy, and the fundamental forces of nature, can be broadly categorized into classical and non-classical (modern) physics. Classical physics, developed from the Renaissance to the late 19th century, focuses on macroscopic phenomena. Non-classical physics, emerging in the early 20th century, addresses microscopic and high-velocity systems where classical theories fail. While understanding of the classical physics and employing the laws of such universe, may utilize the reality and provide functional technology, an alternate understanding of the intellect, wisdom may contribute to an alternate science (Davoudpour, A.R, 2024e). Our understanding of divine presences in the form of prophecies and religious orders are both relevant and contribute to such understanding of the divinity, the hermeneutics (Davoudpour, A.R, 2024b) where the overall function of physical understanding of the humanity ceases to act classically.

Historical Context

Classical physics emerged from the work of pioneers like Isaac Newton, Galileo Galilei, and James Clerk Maxwell. Newton's laws of motion and universal gravitation, along with Maxwell's electromagnetism, formed the bedrock of classical mechanics and electrodynamics.

The limitations of classical physics became apparent in the late 19th century, leading to the development of non-classical physics. Quantum mechanics and relativity, spearheaded by figures like Albert Einstein, Niels Bohr, and Werner Heisenberg, revolutionized our understanding of the universe.

Fundamental Concepts

Classical Physics

1. **Newtonian Mechanics:** Describes the motion of objects under the influence of forces. Newton's laws of motion and gravitation explain planetary motion and everyday phenomena.
2. **Electromagnetism:** Maxwell's equations unify electricity, magnetism, and light as manifestations of the electromagnetic field.
3. **Thermodynamics:** Laws governing energy transfer and conversion, crucial for understanding heat engines and entropy.
4. **Wave Theory:** Describes the behavior of waves, including sound and light, with concepts like interference and diffraction.

Non-Classical Physics

1. **Quantum Mechanics:** Describes the behavior of particles at atomic and subatomic scales. Key principles include wave-particle duality, uncertainty principle, and quantization.
2. **Relativity:** Einstein's theories of special and general relativity address high-velocity and gravitational phenomena. Special relativity introduces concepts of space-time and the speed of light as a constant. General relativity provides a new understanding of gravity as the curvature of space-time.
3. **Quantum Field Theory:** Extends quantum mechanics to fields, explaining particle creation and annihilation, crucial for understanding fundamental forces and particles.
4. **Chaos Theory:** Studies systems highly sensitive to initial conditions, explaining the unpredictability in deterministic systems.

Fundamentals of Metaphysics

In addition to the established branches of physics, alternate metaphysical perspectives provide unique insights into the nature of reality. These perspectives often involve altered states of consciousness or a deeper understanding of the divine as the source of ultimate wisdom (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024e). At the same time such alternate understanding empirically differentiates the virtues of Intellect, wisdom and science in the human challenges (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a) leaving the ground to metaphysical judgements and the framework of religion that cannot be explained by scientific values.

Recognition of the Hell State

One significant aspect of alternate metaphysics is the recognition of the hell state, which can be described as an ocean of suffering in the Buddhist context (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024). This state is characterized by profound existential suffering, far exceeding the conventional understanding of hell as merely physical torment. When a being suffers without remedy, it transcends conventional definitions of hell, highlighting a state of existence where suffering is pervasive and inescapable.

In this state of altered consciousness, the descent from the human state itself signifies hell. This concept challenges the traditional view of hell as a place of punishment and instead suggests a deeper, more existential form of suffering. Conversely, heaven, or the utopia, is not easily understood. One who speaks of an ideal state without experiencing it does not truly comprehend the essence of heaven. This perspective encourages a deeper exploration of the spiritual and existential dimensions of human experience.

Metaphysical Transformations in Physics

As knowledge of the divine presence and its omniscience and omnipresence emerges, the foundations of various disciplines, including physics, mathematics, jurisprudence, and law, undergo transformation. For instance, in classical physics, the equation $E =$

mc^2 assumes the speed of light to be approximately 300,000 km/h. However, with the recognition of the divinity's boundless and borderless nature, the concept of a fixed speed is rendered obsolete.

Divine Presence and Its Implications

The presence of a divine, omniscient, and omnipresent reality fundamentally changes our understanding of speed and distance and consecutively all matters of Physics are affected. In metaphysical terms, if an omnipresent entity exists at points A and B, separated by a classical distance of 100 light years, the concept of distance becomes irrelevant. Thus, in this metaphysical state, the distance between points A and B is considered zero. This transformation renders the equation $E = mc^2$ zero because mainly the speed of light can be considered Zero in the distance of Zero between Point A and Point B additionally mass and volume become insignificant over infinite distances. Consequently, we encounter a null state where energy, mass, and distance cease to exist in their classical definitions.

Implications for Fundamental Physics

1. **Reevaluation of Constants:** The omnipresence of the divine suggests that the constants of physics, such as the speed of light, may not be absolute but relative to the observer's state of consciousness. This challenges the invariance of physical constants and proposes a model where these constants are influenced by metaphysical states.
2. **Altered Definitions of Space and Time:** The concept of space and time undergoes a profound shift. In the presence of the divine, the traditional metrics of space and time dissolve, leading to a reinterpretation where distances and durations are no longer absolute. This aligns with the ideas presented in theories of relativity and quantum mechanics, where the observer's frame of reference significantly affects physical measurements.
3. **From Classical to Metaphysical Physics:** The transition from classical to metaphysical physics involves redefining the fundamental principles of the universe. Here, non-classical equations such as $E = mc^2$ are not only discarded but are reinterpreted within a framework that includes metaphysical considerations. This perspective invites a synthesis of science and

spirituality, where the boundaries between the physical and metaphysical realms blur.

Conclusion

The evolution from classical to non-classical physics and ultimately metaphysics represents a paradigm shift in our understanding of the universe. We already know that in the beginning metaphysical considerations has been implemented in philosophical and scientific works which has been replaced either by the religious view of the divinity or pure materialistic and physical perspectives. The modern crisis in humanity i.e. in Gaza shows that religious and scientific views of the universe do not provide certain capacity to understand the consequences and framework of each other and actions. While classical physics provides a robust framework for macroscopic phenomena, non-classical physics addresses the limitations of classical theories, offering insights into the microscopic and high-velocity realms and the metaphysics annuls the foundation of both classical and non-classical physics. The integration of alternate metaphysical perspectives with traditional physics opens new avenues for understanding reality and post-reality. The recognition of hell state (suffering) and the transformative impact of divine knowledge challenge and expand our conventional understanding of the universe. By redefining the concepts of null speed, distance, and fundamental constants, these metaphysical insights pave the way for a more profound comprehension of the cosmos.

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Empirical Distinctions between Science and Wisdom in the Gaza Crisis

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Abstract

This paper examines the interplay between hikmat (wisdom) and scientific achievements, focusing on their representation in Persian and Arabic literature and their practical implications in contemporary conflicts, such as in Gaza. Hikmat, encompassing moral and practical wisdom, is a central theme in Persian educational literature and is reflected in the works of Jahili poets in Arabic literature (Mohseni Nia & Maryami, 2011; Abdul Jalil, 2001). This wisdom, as defined by Dehkhoda and others, involves understanding life issues and living ethically (Musaheb, 1966). In contrast, science, characterized by empirical methodologies and the pursuit of universal truths (Kuhn, 1970; Popper, 1959), often lacks the ethical and experiential dimensions of wisdom. The paper compares the wisdom of Solomon in the Bible and the Quran, highlighting his exemplary qualities and divine favor in both texts. The Biblical Solomon is acknowledged for his wisdom but ultimately succumbs to personal failings, whereas the Quranic Solomon remains a steadfast prophet (1 Kings; Quran 27:20-44). The comparison illustrates distinct theological and literary traditions. Furthermore, the paper discusses how scientific advancements, while providing significant benefits, can be misused for destructive purposes, as seen in the Gaza conflict (2023-2024), which exemplifies the divergence and potential conflict between science and wisdom. The study concludes by emphasizing the need for integrating scientific progress with wisdom to ensure ethical and humane outcomes. The Gaza conflict serves as a stark reminder of the consequences when scientific achievements are not guided by wisdom and ethical considerations. Future research

should explore the integration of these domains to foster a more holistic approach to human progress.

Keywords: Gaza, Solomon, Hikmat, Wisdom

Introduction

Hikmat and wisdom are two similar categories that have a wide range of poems and works in Persian and Arabic literature. (Musaheb, 1966) has been interpreted and in another place, knowledge of life issues and how to live has been defined. According to Dekhoda, wisdom has also been defined as the understanding of wisdom and cleverness. Arising from the thoughts of various moralists, it forms an important branch of Persian literature called the educational literature of Iran (Mohseni Nia, Naser, and Maryami, Elham. 2011). . The ascetic advice and teachings form this literature. The verse and prose, which sometimes came under the independent title of Andznameh, and sometimes brought a wise story to the field of education and learning, in Arabic literature, we witness the manifestation of wisdom and wisdom in the works of Jahili poets. The way of thoughts and intellectual development of poets and the range of their understanding was related to human issues and the mysteries of existence. Wisdom is made in prose, and its most important topics are around the death of forgiveness, the fate of man and the events of the times" (Abd al-Jalil, 2001). Therefore, at first sight, the wisdom of ignorance can be considered as the result of the experience of an ignorant person during his life. Jahili art is the reflections and observations of Jahili poets, which are in a verse of a poem or a phrase in the hand of the city with phrases and studies Independence has not become and it can be achieved through different purposes. Solomon, known for his wisdom and wealth, is a prominent figure in both the Bible and the Quran. His narratives in these texts highlight his exemplary qualities, his rule, and his relationship with God. The distinction between science and wisdom has intrigued philosophers, psychologists, and scholars across disciplines. While science seeks to understand the natural world through rigorous methodologies, wisdom is concerned with the application of knowledge in a manner that is judicious and morally

sound. This paper aims to clarify these concepts, considering their definitions, methodologies, and roles in human decision-making.

Solomon in the Bible

In the Bible, Solomon is the son of David and Bathsheba, and he succeeds David as king of Israel. His story is primarily found in the books of 1 Kings and 2 Chronicles. Solomon is renowned for his wisdom, which is divinely bestowed. According to 1 Kings 3:5-14, Solomon asks God for an understanding heart to judge the people and distinguish between right and wrong. Pleased with Solomon's request, God grants him unparalleled wisdom, along with riches and honor.

Solomon's wisdom is demonstrated in various anecdotes, such as the famous judgment where he discerns the true mother of a baby claimed by two women (1 Kings 3:16-28). Furthermore, Solomon is credited with composing many Proverbs, Ecclesiastes, and the Song of Solomon, showcasing his literary and philosophical contributions.

He also undertakes the grand project of building the Temple in Jerusalem, which becomes the central place of worship for the Israelites (1 Kings 6-7). Despite his many accomplishments, Solomon's reign is not without flaws. His later years are marked by his marriages to many foreign women who lead him into idolatry, angering God and leading to the eventual division of the kingdom (1 Kings 11:1-13).

Solomon in the Quran

In the Quran, Solomon (Sulayman) is depicted as a prophet and a king endowed with wisdom, knowledge, and the ability to communicate with animals and jinn. His story appears in several surahs, including Al-Baqarah (2:102), An-Naml (27:15-44), and Saba' (34:12-14).

The Quran emphasizes Solomon's wisdom and his just rule. In Surah An-Naml, Solomon's communication with the ant and his interaction with the Queen of Sheba (Bilqis) are highlighted. He learns from a hoopoe bird about the Queen of Sheba's sun worship,

and he sends her a letter inviting her to worship Allah. The queen, impressed by Solomon's wisdom and the grandeur of his court, ultimately submits to Allah (Quran 27:20-44).

Solomon's ability to control the wind and command jinn is also noted in the Quran. These supernatural abilities underscore his unique status and the divine favor he enjoys (Quran 34:12-14). Unlike the Biblical account, the Quran does not mention Solomon's fall into idolatry, instead focusing on his devotion to God and his role as a wise and powerful ruler.

Comparative Analysis

Both the Bible and the Quran portray Solomon as a wise and powerful ruler with a unique relationship with the divine. However, there are notable differences in their narratives. The Biblical Solomon is a figure whose wisdom is acknowledged but who ultimately succumbs to personal and spiritual failings. In contrast, the Quranic Solomon remains a steadfast prophet whose wisdom and piety are consistently emphasized.

The Bible provides a more humanized portrayal of Solomon, complete with his strengths and weaknesses, illustrating the complexities of his character and reign. The Quran, however, presents Solomon as an idealized prophet, emphasizing his role as a model of wisdom and faithfulness to God.

These differing portrayals reflect the distinct theological and literary traditions of the Bible and the Quran. While both texts recognize Solomon's significance, they each highlight different aspects of his life and character to convey their respective religious messages.

1. **Defining Science and Wisdom**
2. **Science:** Science is a systematic enterprise that builds and organizes knowledge in the form of testable explanations and predictions

about the universe (Kuhn, 1970). It relies on empirical evidence, the scientific method, and peer review to validate findings. Science is dynamic, evolving with new discoveries and technological advancements (Popper, 1959).

3. **Wisdom:** Wisdom is often described as the ability to make sound judgments and decisions based on knowledge, experience, and understanding of life's complexities (Aristotle, 350 BCE). It encompasses aspects of cognitive, reflective, and moral dimensions, integrating knowledge with practical, ethical, and existential considerations (Baltes & Staudinger, 2000).

Methodologies and Epistemologies

1. **Scientific Methodology:** The scientific method involves formulating hypotheses, conducting experiments, observing outcomes, and drawing conclusions that can be replicated and tested (Feyerabend, 1975). It emphasizes objectivity, reproducibility, and falsifiability (Popper, 1959).
2. **Wisdom's Approach:** Wisdom does not adhere to a fixed methodology. Instead, it involves integrating diverse sources of knowledge and experience, often through introspection, deliberation, and empathy (Sternberg, 1990). Wisdom is contextual and value-laden, requiring judgment that balances various factors, including emotional intelligence and ethical principles (Ardelt, 2003).

Comparative Analysis

1. **Nature of Knowledge:**
 - **Science:** Focuses on factual, verifiable knowledge that can be generalized across different contexts (Kuhn, 1970).
 - **Wisdom:** Incorporates experiential knowledge, intuition, and values, often dealing with the "why" and "what is good" rather than the "what is" (Baltes & Staudinger, 2000).
2. **Goal Orientation:**

- **Science:** Aims at uncovering universal laws and theories, contributing to the expansion of knowledge (Popper, 1959).
- **Wisdom:** Seeks to enhance the quality of human life, promoting well-being and ethical living through practical reasoning (Aristotle, 350 BCE).

3. **Methodological Rigor vs. Practical Insight:**

- **Science:** Relies on empirical testing and statistical analysis to establish causality and correlation (Feyerabend, 1975).
- **Wisdom:** Emphasizes holistic understanding, often relying on judgment and experience over empirical data (Sternberg, 1990).

Intersections and Integration

Despite their differences, science and wisdom are not mutually exclusive. Advances in science can inform wise decisions, and wisdom can guide scientific inquiry by emphasizing the ethical implications and societal impact of scientific progress (Habermas, 1971). For instance, the development of medical technologies must be guided by ethical considerations to ensure they benefit humanity without causing harm (Boorse, 1975).

The Battle Between Scientific Achievements and Wisdom in Gaza"

Scientific achievements in the West have been used to restrict, damage, and finally commit horrible crimes in Gaza over the last decades, especially in the crimes against humanity between 2023-2024, which contribute to the first televised genocide in history in the 21st century. *The Book of Solomon* (The Holy Bible) a canonical Jewish and Biblical narrative, directly advises followers to avoid tyranny and crimes and warns of their consequences. However, the battle in Gaza exemplifies an instance where wisdom and science confront each other in conflicts, highlighting a significant separation between the two. The wars of wisdom can be considered as wars with the source of wisdom (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024) or supra-human beings (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024) and prior achievements of

the humanity in the pursuit of wisdom i.e. the battle against apartheid (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024).

Conclusion

In conclusion, while science and wisdom serve different purposes and employ distinct methodologies, they are interrelated in their pursuit of understanding and improving human life. Science provides the tools and knowledge necessary for innovation and progress, while wisdom ensures that such advancements are aligned with human values and ethical standards. Future research should explore how these domains can be integrated to foster a more holistic approach to human knowledge and decision-making. Finally the war in Gaza (2023 – 2024) is a clear instance of battle between biblical wisdoms and science which is a clear indication of a determinative separation (despite their interrelation for individual pursuit) for the involving parties, especially for the Israeli so called religious propaganda.

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God, Teacher, Nation and the Importance of Transcendental Jurisdiction to Quran

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Abstract:

We try to elaborate the importance of transcendental jurisdiction to Quran in order to determine the hermeneutics and the language of Quran. Without such jurisdiction a vague gap of darkness implying the platonic realm of ignorance rises in the Islamic nations which causes chaos and distractions. We also try resolve the linguistics of the resurrection of teacher in Quran and answer allegory of David in Quran and the question of existence of Israel prophesized by a philosophical question in Quran and determine the platonic state of ignorance caused in Islamic nations by unawareness of the transcendental truth and hermeneutics within Quran.

Keywords: Allegory of David, Consciousness

The Value of Honor to Wisdom: A Philosophical Reflection

King and Teacher's legacy:

In the annals of history, we often find contrasting lives that provoke deep contemplation about the nature of honor and wisdom. One such contemplation arises from the tale of a king and a teacher, presenting us with profound questions about the essence of life and the true foundation of the world.

The king, a figure of immense power and authority, killed thousands and ruled with an iron fist. His reign was marked by judgments and flourishing prosperity, and upon his death, he was lauded by all, even his enemies. His legacy was one of strength and dominance, earning him widespread acclaim and respect.

In stark contrast, the teacher lived a life of poverty and asceticism. For a hundred years, he taught and learned, fasting frequently and abstaining from worldly pleasures. Despite his dedication to knowledge and spiritual practice, he garnered neither respect from his relatives and companions nor accumulated any wealth. When he passed away, his name was forgotten, unmentioned by those he had impacted.

Witnessing these contrasting fates, a judge pondered deeply, asking both himself and God: "Who deserves honor? And what is the value of knowledge and wisdom?" This question underscores the perplexing nature of human recognition and the inherent value of intellectual and spiritual pursuits.

In this contemplation, the judge draws a comparison between the teacher and the ruler, questioning the very foundation of the world and the essence of honor. To delve deeper, we turn to the philosophical insights of Plato and the teachings of the Quran.

Plato's Duality of Existence

Plato's philosophy speaks of a duality in existence, dividing the world into the realm of truth and the realm of appearances. The world of truth, or the world of forms, is where the essence of events unfolds. This concept is exemplified in various sacred texts and teachings.

Quranic Insights

Surah Al-Jumu'ah, Verse 2, states:

"هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيِّينَ رَسُولًا مِنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ وَالْحِكْمَةَ وَإِنْ كَانُوا مِنْ قَبْلُ لَفِي ضَلَالٍ مُبِينٍ"

"He is the One who sent among the unlettered a Messenger from themselves, reciting to them His verses, purifying them, and teaching them the Book and wisdom, although they were in clear error before."

The word "بعث" reflects a state of resurrection "در فارسی رستاخیر" and has been used by the governments in Iran, Iraq and Syria to determine revolutionary actions during Pahlavi dynasty and Saddam Hussain and still is ruling in Syria with Baas party of Bashar al-Asad.

This verse highlights the importance of teaching and purification in the realm of truth. It aligns with Plato's allegory of the cave, where individuals in darkness (error) cannot grasp the truth unless someone enlightened exits the cave and returns to guide them.

The Linguistic and Philosophical Roots of "بعث"

The Arabic word "بعث" (ba'ath) holds deep connotations of resurrection, awakening, and revival. In linguistic and philosophical terms, "بعث" signifies a state of bringing something back to life or initiating a new beginning from a dormant or suppressed state. This concept is not only relevant in religious and cultural contexts but also finds significant application in political ideologies and movements.

Political Utilization in the Middle East

In the 20th and 21st centuries, the concept of "بعث" and its Persian analogue "رستاخیر" were appropriated by political movements in several Middle Eastern countries, notably Iran, Iraq, and Syria, to signify revolutionary actions and ideological transformations. This term became particularly prominent during the regimes of the Pahlavi dynasty in Iran, Saddam Hussein in Iraq, and the ongoing governance of Bashar al-Assad in Syria.

During the Pahlavi dynasty (1925-1979), the notion of "بعث" was embodied in efforts to modernize and secularize Iran. The dynasty sought to resurrect Persian nationalism and cultural identity,

transforming Iran into a contemporary nation-state. This process involved extensive social, economic, and political reforms aimed at reviving the country's historical legacy and integrating it into the modern world.

In Iraq, the Ba'ath Party, led by Saddam Hussein, explicitly adopted the term "بعث" to denote its revolutionary ideology. Founded in 1947, the Ba'ath Party aimed to achieve Arab unity and socialism through radical transformation. The party's name itself, Hizb al-Ba'ath al-Arabi al-Ishtiraki (Arab Socialist Ba'ath Party), reflects this ideology of resurrection and renewal. Under Saddam Hussein's rule (1979-2003), Iraq underwent significant political and social changes, often characterized by authoritarianism and aggressive nationalism.

Similarly, in Syria, the Ba'ath Party has been a dominant force since the 1960s. Bashar al-Assad's regime continues to rule under the Ba'athist ideology, promoting a blend of Arab nationalism, socialism, and secularism. The term "بعث" in this context represents the ongoing efforts to maintain and revitalize the nation's identity and political structure amidst internal and external challenges.

The Journey Toward Enlightenment

The behavior of cave dwellers—repetition, resistance, or fear—parallels the human condition in the face of truth. True enlightenment requires a vertical ascent in life, moving beyond mere day-to-day existence. Historical and mythical figures like Khidr, Gilgamesh, Aeneas, Perseus, and Dante exemplify this quest for enlightenment.

Sacred texts, including the Quran, hold the essence of many concepts and values. Their true understanding necessitates enlightenment, a journey from darkness to light. This raises the question: Should the Quran have been revealed, considering the state of error in which it was received?

The Allegory of David in Quran

﴿اصْبِرْ عَلٰی مَا يَقُولُوْنَ وَ اذْكُرْ عِبْدَنَا دَاوُدَ ذَا الْاَيْدِ اِنَّهُ اَوَّابٌ (17) اِنَّا سَخَّرْنَا الْجِبَالَ مَعَهُ يُسَبِّحْنَ بِالْعُثْبِيِّ وَ الْاَشْرَاقِ (18) وَ الطَّيْرَ مَخْشُوْرَةً كُلٌّ لِّهٗ اَوَّابٌ (19) وَ شَدَدْنَا مُلْكَهُ وَ اَتَيْنَاهُ الْحِكْمَةَ وَ فَصَّلَ الْخُطَابِ (20) وَ هَلْ اَتَاكَ نَبَاُ الْخَصْمِ اِذْ تَسُوْرُوْا الْمُحْرَابَ (21) اِذْ

دَخَلُوا عَلَي دَاوُدَ فَفَزِعَ مِنْهُمْ قَالُوا لَا تَحْفَ خَصْمَانِ بَغِي بَعْضُنَا عَلَي بَعْضٍ فَاذْكُم بَيْنِنَا بِالْحَقِّ وَ لَا تُشْطِطْ وَ اِهْدِنَا اِلَي سَوَاءِ الصِّرَاطِ (22) اِنَّ هَذَا اَخِي لَهُ تَسْعٌ وَ تِسْعُونَ نَعْجَةً وَ لِي نَعْجَةٌ وَ اِحِدَةٌ فَقَالَ اَكْفُلْنِيهَا وَ عَزَّنِي فِي الْخِطَابِ (23) قَالَ لَقَدْ ظَلَمَكَ بِسُؤَالِ نَعَجَتِكَ اِلَي نِعَاجِهِ وَ اِنَّ كَثِيْرًا مِّنَ الْخُلَطَاءِ لَيَبْغِي بَعْضُهُمْ عَلَي بَعْضٍ اِلَّا الَّذِيْنَ اٰمَنُوْا وَ عَمِلُوْا (24) الصَّالِحَاتِ وَ قَلِيْلٌ مَّا هُمْ وَ ظَنَّ دَاوُدُ اَنَّمَا فَتَنَّاهُ فَاسْتَغْفَرَ رَبَّهُ وَ خَرَّ رَاكِعًا وَ اٰنَابَ

The allegory of David in Surah Sad (Verses 17 to 24) illustrates a profound lesson. Angels question whether a sheep should be given to an angel who already has many sheep's. The lesson lies not in the literal interpretation but in the elevation of intellect and understanding of justice and wisdom which comes to truth thousands of years later, and questions whether the Israel has the right to be a single vessel within many vessels in the Islamic world.

Conclusion

The contemplation of the judge—reflecting on the lives of the king and the teacher—leads us to profound philosophical and spiritual insights. It challenges us to reconsider the foundations of honor and wisdom, urging us to seek true enlightenment and recognize the essential role of enlightened teachers in our journey toward understanding.

Such understanding of the esoteric Quran “has even a greater impact on the the popular slogan of the Monarchism “God, King, Nation” and transforms it to a different realm, the realm of wisdom and education. God, the teacher, the nation.

Deep and at the same time hermeneutics in Quran marks it dark and untouchable without a transcendental knowledge, and the Quran itself admits to such darkness "لَا يَمَسُّهُ اِلَّا الْمُطَهَّرُوْنَ فِي كِتَابٍ مَّكْنُوْنٍ" (Al-Waqi'ah: 78-79) making it vague and untouchable for those without jurisdiction to Quran, be it the spiritual leaders or normal people who have not been enlightened. The essence of the Quran lies in its layers of enlightenment and darkness, guiding those who seek true understanding.

Justification of Spiritual Governments and Their Challenges from a Jungian and Gnostic Perspective: Psycho-Spiritual Wars

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Abstract:

This article examines the justifications and challenges associated with spiritual governments through a Jungian lens, particularly focusing on the intersection of psycho-spiritual dynamics and political power. Drawing on historical and contemporary examples, including the role of religious and spiritual figures in governance, the paper explores how spiritual concepts can become politicized and the resultant psycho-spiritual conflicts. By analyzing historical instances such as the use of spiritual symbols by totalitarian regimes and the current political climate in Iran, this study aims to illuminate the complex interplay between spiritual authority and political power, highlighting the inherent risks and psychological battles involved.

Keywords: Karl Jung, Governance, Spirituality

Introduction:

The phenomenon of spiritual governance, wherein religious or spiritual authority is entwined with political power, has been a recurring theme throughout history. This paper builds upon earlier discussions (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) regarding the theme of innate

governance, additionally,, previously we have published an article¹ which analyzed the use of spiritual titles and positions by politicians to craft social identity and legitimacy. By delving into Jungian psychology and its relevance to spiritual governance, we seek to understand the underlying psycho-spiritual conflicts and challenges associated with such systems. Iranian and Persian speaking scholars have insisted on a purification of inner psych rather than involvement in the outer conflict. Amongst them Nezami Ganjei has openly discussed the inner challenges in his popular poem:

" چون شیر به خود سپه شکن باش

فرزند خصال خویشان باش"²

Historical Context and Theoretical Framework:

1. **Spirituality and Governance:** The integration of spiritual or religious titles into governance has been a strategy employed by various political leaders to consolidate power and legitimize their rule. For instance, the concept of "Velayat-e Faqih" (Guardianship of the Jurist) in Iran serves as a contemporary example where spiritual and political authority intersect. In the Middle East, the popular belief in "God, Teacher, and Nation" has been a central tenet of Islam for centuries. Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) was and continues to be regarded as the central teacher through whom transcendental guidance has been delivered to humanity (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024).
2. **Jungian Psychology and the Spirit:** Carl Jung's theories on the collective unconscious and archetypes provide a useful framework for understanding the psychological implications of spiritual governance. Jung's concept of the "inner dragon" or the "inner god"

¹ *The Theory of Velayat-e Faqih of Mr. Khomeini and the Farashgard of Mr. Reza Pahlavi - Riding the Untamed Horse of Spiritual Authorities*, Azadi News" on July 23, 2019,

<https://www.azadineews.net/2019/07/23/%d9%86%d8%b8%d8%b1%db%8c%d9%87-%d9%88%d9%84%db%8c-%d9%81%d9%82%db%8c%d9%87-%d8%a2%d9%82%d8%a7%db%8c-%d8%ae%d9%85%db%8c%d9%86%db%8c-%d9%88-%d9%81%d8%b1%d8%b4%da%af%d8%b1%d8%af-%d8%a2%d9%82%d8%a7%db%8c/> [In Persian]

² Be made of your inner self, Overcome the legions within yourself like a lion, Nezami Ganjei, also known as Nizami Ganjavi (1141-1209), was a Persian poet from Ganja (present-day Azerbaijan). He is considered one of the greatest romantic epic poets in Persian literature. His most famous work is the "Khamseh" or "Quintet," a collection of five long narrative poems that include "Layla and Majnun" and "Khosrow and Shirin." Nezami's storytelling prowess, vivid imagery, and profound philosophical insights have made his works enduring classics in Persian and world literature.

reflects the idea that individuals and societies may project their internal spiritual struggles onto external political and social structures.

Case Studies:

1. Historical Examples:

- **Nazi Germany:** The use of the swastika, an ancient spiritual symbol, by Adolf Hitler's regime exemplifies how spiritual symbols can be appropriated for political ends, leading to catastrophic consequences. This historical precedent underscores the dangers of conflating spiritual and political ideologies.
- **The Shah's Iran:** Reza Shah Pahlavi's efforts to modernize Iran by distancing the state from spiritual authority represent an attempt to secularize governance while maintaining some spiritual elements for national cohesion.

2. Contemporary Analysis:

- **Iran's Current Regime:** The current political climate in Iran, under the leadership of Ayatollah Khamenei, reflects a continuation of the integration of spiritual and political authority. The regime's stance towards external adversaries, particularly in relation to Israel and Zionism, demonstrates the continuation of the historical trend of projecting internal spiritual conflicts onto external political struggles.

Jungian Interpretation and Implications:

- 1. Psycho-Spiritual Wars:** Empirical and social observation suggests that the integration of spiritual ideals into governance can lead to intense psycho-spiritual conflicts (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024). This is particularly evident in situations where a regime projects its internal struggles and spiritual crises onto external enemies. The concept of the "inner dragon" or "inner god" becoming a public figure or symbol of authority can create a dangerous conflation of spiritual and political realms.
- 2. The Cost of Spiritual Wars:** As E. Iqbal Lahori's poetry suggests, the internal spiritual struggle is a path to self-purification and enlightenment. In contrast, spiritual governments often externalize these conflicts, leading to prolonged and costly external

confrontations. The Iranian regime's current policies may thus be seen as a manifestation of internal spiritual struggles projected onto the geopolitical stage.

Conclusion:

The examination of spiritual governance through a Jungian and Gnostic perspective reveals significant psycho-spiritual challenges and risks. The integration of spiritual authority into political systems can lead to intense internal conflicts ascended for centuries, which are often externalized through political and military actions. Historical and contemporary examples illustrate the complex interplay between spiritual and political power, highlighting the need for a nuanced understanding of how spiritual concepts impact governance and international relations.

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Haman Project and Infiltration of Pseudo-Clerics in Iran: A Theoretical Perspective on Intelligence Practices

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Abstract

This research article explores the creation and utilization of pseudo-clerics in Iran, a strategy employed by various intelligence agencies to infiltrate and manipulate the socio-political and religious landscape. We previously explained multiple aspects of the so-called "Mahan" or "Haman" plan to increase distrust among the people and the "Mahan" psychological operation plan, implemented by the SAVAK security advisor in the late Pahlavi regime under the military government of General Gholam Reza Azhari. The operation, suggested by Mossad, aimed to ridicule religious beliefs among the Iranian populace. The plan which involved utilizing pseudo-clerics to propagate false religious visions has not been ceased. The article sheds light on the psychological and social ramifications of such practices in the Islamic Republic of Iran.

Keywords: Pseudo-clergy, Mossad, Iran, Psychological warfare

Introduction

In recent decades, the Islamic Republic of Iran has faced numerous challenges to its religious and political integrity. One of the more insidious threats has been the infiltration of pseudo-clerics—individuals posing as religious scholars with the intent to disrupt and manipulate the socio-political order mainly by accelerating distrust and social dissatisfaction amongst the government (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024). This strategy, referred to as the "Haman Project," has roots in the complex history of intelligence practices and psychological warfare aimed at undermining religious and political stability (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024). While espionage is generally forbidden from an Islamic perspective (Davoudpour, 2024), such practices have historical roots in Jewish communities, where they are sometimes praised or implemented. This is exemplified in the story of Esther and Haman found in the Hebrew Bible, which underscores the strategic use of intelligence and infiltration in Jewish history (Littman, 2008; Ginsburg, 2009).

Historical Background

The Islamic Revolution and Ideological Shift

The Islamic Republic of Iran, founded in 1979 following the Islamic Revolution, initially drew its ideological foundation from prominent figures such as Ayatollah Mahmoud Taleghani, Ali Shariati, and Mohammad Beheshti. These ideologues emphasized a blend of religious and philosophical thought aimed at creating a just and progressive society. However, over time, the regime's focus shifted towards a more rigid and doctrinal interpretation of Shi'a Islam, emphasizing rituals and practices that were not prioritized before the revolution, such as extensive mourning ceremonies (Ashura) and strict dress codes (hijab enforcement) (Abrahamian, 2008).

Emergence of Pseudo-Clerics

The transition towards a doctrinal and ritualistic state created an environment where the educational system in religious seminaries (Hawzas) produced a high number of graduates. This phenomenon was partly due to the regime's satisfaction with the proliferation of pan-Shi'a students and their dissatisfaction with the more philosophical and ideological thinkers. Consequently, this environment facilitated the infiltration of pseudo-clerics—

individuals who could easily proclaim their conversion to Islam with the simple recitation of the Shahada (the Islamic declaration of faith), a process simpler than in many other religions (Keddie, 2006).

The Haman Project

Objectives and Strategies

The Haman Project as explained in earlier research (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) represents a concerted effort by intelligence agencies to exploit the religious and social framework of Iran. The project's primary objectives included:

1. **Spiritual Degradation:** Introducing false religious teachings to create confusion and diminish genuine spiritual values.
2. **Social Dissatisfaction:** Utilizing pseudo-clerics to sow discord and dissatisfaction within society.
3. **Political Manipulation:** Infiltrating political and religious institutions to influence policy and decision-making processes (Dabashi, 2011).

These pseudo-clerics often exhibited significant intelligence and acumen, enabling them to ascend the theoretical and practical ranks within the religious and political systems.

Implementation and Impact

The implementation of the Haman Project involved the creation and dissemination of misleading religious texts, particularly those concerning the concept of Mahdism (belief in the Mahdi, a messianic figure in Islam), and stringent interpretations of Sharia law. These actions contributed to widespread dissatisfaction and spiritual disillusionment among the populace. The pseudo-clerics' role in this strategy was crucial, as their perceived legitimacy allowed them to influence both public opinion and policy effectively (Takeyh, 2009).

The Role of Pseudo-Clerics in Politics

Infiltration Strategies

Pseudo-clerics have played a crucial role in the political sphere of Iran, effectively using their religious guise to penetrate key institutions. This infiltration often involved:

1. **Assuming Leadership Positions:** Pseudo-clerics have occupied significant positions within governmental and semi-governmental organizations, leveraging their influence to sway policy decisions.
2. **Mobilizing Support:** By exploiting their religious status, pseudo-clerics have mobilized groups within society, often inciting or manipulating public opinion to support governmental agendas.

Social and Political Dismantling

The role of pseudo-clerics extends beyond mere infiltration; they have been instrumental in dismantling established social and governmental structures. By promoting divisive ideologies and undermining traditional values, they have contributed to a fragmented social fabric (Dabashi, 2011).

Case Studies

There are few or no in-depth case studies focusing on pseudo-clergy within the sphere of Iranian politics, media—including private broadcasting companies—often disseminates baseless and malevolent theological practices. These activities frequently involve unknown sources of funding and can contribute to the erosion of public trust and social cohesion. To effectively address these issues, a more comprehensive and detailed study is necessary. Such research would help identify effective strategies to protect the integrity of societal and psychological order from the disruptive influence of pseudo-clerical practices.

Conclusion

The infiltration and manipulation by pseudo-clerics, as part of the broader Haman Project, have had profound implications for the Islamic Republic of Iran. This strategy, rooted in historical intelligence practices, has effectively undermined religious integrity, fostered social dissatisfaction, and manipulated political processes. Understanding the origins and impacts of such practices

is crucial for developing countermeasures to protect the socio-political and religious fabric of Iran. While we cannot mention any direct names or case studies due to limitation of the field work in this matter, it is evident that some of the extreme practices in the political context have directly damaged the integrity of the Iranian social Plato and led to significant Socio-psychological disorders.

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Religion: The Significant and Enigmatic Divine Philosophy, In the Primordial Perfection of God

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Abstract

Religion has captivated billions for millennia, blending divine intoxication and cathexis with a set of contradictory and complementary commandments that shape and bestow identities upon its followers. This exploration delves into the enigmatic aspects of religion, highlighting its indefinable elements such as dreams, revelations, and allegories, which sustain interpretations over time while remaining unresolved mysteries. The paper contrasts religious paradoxes with philosophical contradictions, showcasing examples like Zeno's paradox and the fate of Ahura Mazda in Iranian traditions. It examines religion's role as a complex human laboratory where the divine wisdom surpasses human understanding, influencing global socio-economic dynamics, as exemplified by the transformation of the Kaaba. Additionally, the distinction between religious and philosophical paradoxes is explored, emphasizing the mystical elements that challenge empirical reasoning. Popular culture, as seen in "Avatar," reflects these themes, underscoring the concept of a perfect God from the beginning, complete without need for further perfection. The discussion extends to the philosophical notion of divine perfection, the interplay between the created and the teacher, and the journey towards regaining a paradisiacal state, illustrating the inherent complexity and profundity of religious truths. Through this analysis, religion emerges as

a profound framework for understanding existence, identity, and the divine, continuously shaping human thought and society.

Keywords: Religion, Theological paradoxes

Introduction

Religion has captivated, subdued, and enthralled billions of people for thousands of years. The religious fervor, accompanied by a sense of sanctity and purity, acts as a form of divine intoxication and cathexis. Cathexis refers to the pleasure derived from philosophy (Freud, 1914). Religion comprises a set of contradictory, conflicting, similar, and sometimes complementary commandments. These not only emerge from the local identities of people but also bestow identities upon them (Durkheim, 1912).

The Indefinable Aspect of Religion

Certain aspects of religion, such as dreams, revelations, allegories, and intuitions, are inherently indefinable. For instance, the vision of John in the canonical book of Revelations speaks of the Lamb of God, or the story of Saleh's camel, which, while seemingly simple, are ultimately complex in their metaphorical nature (Ferguson, 2018). This intriguing simplicity initially strikes the human mind, sustains interpretations for extended periods, and finally remains an unsolved mystery (Eliade, 1987).

Religious Paradoxes and Philosophical Contradictions

In philosophy, paradoxes like Zeno's paradox exist, but in religion, the number of these paradoxes is countless. An example from Iranian religions is the fate of Ahura Mazda in the battle against Ahriman, which is one of these paradoxes (Boyce, 1987). Religious paradoxes serve to challenge the believer's understanding and provoke deeper contemplation (Kierkegaard, 1843). The extent of such paradoxes in the religious text renders them as a so called

Matrix which we consider a divine metaphorical wisdom (Davoudpour, A. R. , 2024)

The Human Element in Religion

Scholars of religion believe they are studying religion and its commandments, though the human aspect of religion appears straightforward. Even if we accept the entrance of deceitful wills into religion, religion remains a difficult path and a human laboratory where humans are the test subjects. The intelligence and wisdom inherent in religion surpass human understanding (Eliade, 1987). This complexity is highlighted by the various interpretations and practices observed across different cultures and societies (Geertz, 1973).

The Economic and Social Role of Religion

Transforming the Kaaba into the world's largest economic and tourist hub by Allah and Muhammad (PBUH) is just one of the living miracles of Islam (Peters, 1994). Despite this, as we see, religion has been downgraded during times of human simplicity, when technology, social networks, and science were absent, creating an immense and eternal power that did not require technology. The socio-economic impact of religious sites continues to shape global tourism and commerce (Henderson, 2003).

Religious Versus Philosophical Paradoxes

As previously mentioned, religious paradoxes are incredibly complex compared to philosophical paradoxes, where elements operate simply and logically. In religious paradoxes, angels overcome gravity and fly, whereas philosophy (science) can only ignore gravity in the void and nothingness of abstract human existence (Plantinga, 2000). The distinction between the mystical and the empirical underscores the broader differences between religious and philosophical thought (James, 1902).

Depictions in Popular Culture

The film and animation "Avatar" (Hollywood) unveil the astonishing simplicity of advanced beings. The idea that an advanced being finds everything within itself and discovers the evolution of thought and action of God in the first word of God is not far-fetched. This implies that the perfect God was complete in the beginning and does not need to complete Himself in the end (Cameron, 2009). This portrayal resonates with themes in religious and mystical traditions that emphasize inner enlightenment and self-discovery (Campbell, 1949).

The Concept of Perfection in Religion

How is God perfect from the beginning? Because the assumption of divinity is infallibility. The true God does not need the final word; the true God is present from the beginning to the end, but two truths move in creation: one is the created, and the other is the teacher (Lord) (Tillich, 1957). Understanding such a truth is so difficult that it requires profound spiritual insight and contemplation (Buber, 1923).

Example: Can one see with closed eyes?

There must be a way to see with closed eyes. The reason for this question initially comes with two questions: isn't the soul separate from the body? Does the soul need material eyes? These questions echo the spiritual inquiries that have pervaded religious philosophy for centuries (Rumi, 13th century).

The Journey to Perfection

Another point we mentioned is that perfection is in the first house, and reaching it is in the last house. How is it possible to regain the paradise we were in after thousands of trials? The peace, joy, and self-sufficiency, along with fulfilling the needs of childhood, answer the same question of the creation of Adam and Eve in paradise. The more they attain perfection, the farther they move from paradise and comprehend the nature of suffering, difficulty, and awareness.

Why? Because God's philosophy is simply perfect at the beginning; each cell is a world in itself. But rediscovering it by the created and teaching it by the teacher propels the wheel of creation (Nasr, 1996).

Conclusion

Religion, with its inherent contradictions and paradoxes, provides a complex yet profound framework for understanding human existence and the divine. Its role in shaping identities, offering philosophical insights, and influencing socio-economic structures remains unparalleled. The journey towards understanding religious truths is as intricate and infinite as the divine itself.

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Ethical and Security Implications of Governmental Surveillance from Quranic Perspective and Foreign Government; A Comparative Study

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Abstract: Governmental surveillance is increasingly central to state operations worldwide, justified by security imperatives but raising ethical concerns. This article explores these issues through the lens of Quranic principles, particularly Surah Al-Hujurat (49:12), which prohibits spying and malicious gossip. It integrates insights from Israeli, German, and US surveillance policies, legal frameworks, and scholarly literature to examine the ethical complexities and security implications of surveillance technologies.

Keywords: Government Surveillance, Ethics, Quran, Privacy, National Security, Art. 25of the constitution of Islamic Republic of Iran

Introduction: In an era dominated by technological advancements, governmental surveillance has emerged as a critical tool for national security and governance. This paper examines the ethical and security implications of surveillance practices, drawing upon Quranic teachings and comparative analyses of Israeli, German, and US policies. The Quranic injunctions against suspicion and spying (49:12) offer foundational principles that resonate with contemporary debates on privacy, trust, and governance.

With these interpretations, the Quran, in accordance with verse 12 of Surah Al-Hujurat (or The Chambers), addresses the prohibition of espionage, as well as the prevention of suspicion and malicious gossip: "O you who have believed, avoid much [negative] assumption. Indeed, some assumption is sin. And do not spy or backbite each other. Would one of you like to eat the flesh of

his brother when dead? You would detest it. And fear Allah; indeed, Allah is accepting repentance and Merciful"¹.

In accordance with the previous Quranic considerations, Article 25 of the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran, citizens are affirmed the rights to privacy, the sanctity of the home, and the confidentiality of communications. This constitutional provision serves as a fundamental safeguard against any encroachment upon these rights, allowing citizens to seek recourse through legal complaints in instances where these rights are violated.

The right to privacy enshrined in Art. 25 ensures that individuals have the autonomy to protect their personal information and activities from unwarranted intrusion by governmental or non-governmental entities. This includes protections against unauthorized surveillance, monitoring of communications, and unauthorized access to personal spaces such as homes and private property. By explicitly acknowledging these rights, the Iranian Constitution establishes a legal framework that obliges authorities to respect and uphold citizens' privacy rights as a fundamental component of their civil liberties

In practical terms, any violation of these constitutional guarantees can lead to legal actions initiated by affected individuals seeking redress and accountability from the responsible parties. These protections are crucial in maintaining the integrity of personal freedoms and ensuring that citizens can engage in private activities and communications without fear of undue interference or surveillance.

Literature Review: Scholarly discourse on governmental surveillance underscores its dual role in security and privacy domains. Lyon (2007) posits that surveillance operates as a mechanism of social control, while Ball (2016) discusses its ethical dimensions and impact on civil liberties. Additional perspectives from Agamben (2011) critique the normalization of surveillance in modern societies, highlighting its implications for democratic principles.

German Surveillance Policies and Legal Framework: Germany's approach to surveillance is governed by laws such as the 2017 Federal Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz), which regulates the collection and processing of personal data by public authorities (Pfleiderer, 2018). The Federal Constitutional Court has played a crucial role in balancing surveillance powers with privacy rights, emphasizing the importance of proportionality and safeguards against abuse (Bundesverfassungsgericht, 2020).

Israeli Policies and Legal Framework: In Israel, surveillance practices are governed by laws such as the 2007 Intelligence and Security Services Law, which grants extensive powers to security agencies for monitoring and intelligence gathering (Berkovitch, 2018). The Israeli Supreme Court

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اجْتَنِبُوا كَثِيرًا مِّنَ الظَّنِّ إِنَّ بَعْضَ الظَّنِّ إِثْمٌ وَلَا تَجَسَّسُوا وَلَا يَغْتَب بَّعْضُكُم بَعْضًا ۚ أَيُحِبُّ أَحَدُكُمْ أَن يَأْكُلَ لَحْمَ أَخِيهِ مَيْتًا فَكَرِهْتُمُوهُ ۚ ۱
(49:12) وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ ۚ إِنَّ اللَّهَ تَوَّابٌ رَّحِيمٌ

has grappled with balancing security needs and individual rights, often issuing rulings that reflect a nuanced approach to surveillance legality and ethics (Hirsch, 2020).

US Surveillance Practices and Legal Framework: In the United States, surveillance activities are authorized under the Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Act (FISA) of 1978, amended multiple times to expand governmental powers in response to evolving security threats (Stone, 2020). The National Security Agency (NSA) operates under these legal frameworks, conducting electronic surveillance and data collection both domestically and internationally (Bamford, 2018).

Discussion

This study employs a qualitative approach, integrating textual analysis of Quranic verses with critical examination of Iran, German, Israeli, and US surveillance policies. Comparative analysis illuminates how different legal and cultural contexts shape surveillance practices and ethical considerations. The Quranic directive against suspicion and spying (49:12) provides a moral framework for evaluating contemporary surveillance practices and has been deemed ineffective by the obligations of governance in Islamic Republic of Iran.

The ethical dimensions of governmental surveillance intersect with broader debates on privacy rights, civil liberties, and state accountability. German, Israeli, and US policies exemplify varying approaches to balancing security imperatives with individual freedoms, reflecting complex societal values and legal frameworks. Ethical guidelines derived from Quranic teachings offer insights into promoting transparency and accountability in surveillance practices.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, governmental surveillance remains a contentious issue with profound ethical and security implications. Quranic teachings on trust and ethical conduct provide a principled foundation for evaluating surveillance practices globally. German, Israeli, and US policies demonstrate diverse approaches to surveillance legality and ethics, underscoring the need for robust governance frameworks and public discourse to safeguard individual rights amidst security challenges. However it is evident that breaches of the constitutional rights in particular Art. 25 of the constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran takes place.

Our primary review of such concerns prevails that such infringement of the written articles in law takes place in other countries like US, Germany and Israel. Therefore the matter of constitutional rights is deemed ineffective by compulsory and supplementary laws.

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The Evolution of Consciousness: From Eden to the Suffering

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Abstract

This article explores the evolution of human consciousness from an Edenic state of blissful ignorance to a deeper awareness of existential suffering, drawing on insights from Gnostic traditions, Buddhist teachings, and poetic expressions of suffering in Persian and English literature. Arguably, humanity exists in a metaphorical Eden, a paradise free from suffering due to the absence of self-awareness. The awakening of consciousness, as illustrated by the Biblical story of Adam and Eve, marks a departure from this state, bringing an awareness of suffering and mortality. Carl Jung's psychological theories align with this transition, emphasizing the need for individuals to confront and heal their inner suffering for psychological wholeness. This duality suggests that true understanding of the world's nature is accessible only to those conscious of their suffering, while those who remain unaware are trapped in superficial reality. The article also examines the role of suffering in inspiring human rights movements and spiritual practices in Gnostic and Buddhist traditions, which aim for liberation from suffering. The poetic traditions highlight the universality of suffering and its role in the path to enlightenment. Ultimately, the journey from Eden to utopia is marked by an awakening to suffering and the pursuit of transcendence, offering a rich tapestry of insights into the human condition.

Keywords: Suffering, Gnosticism, Awakening, Consciousness

Introduction

The concept of Eden, a state of bliss and ignorance, juxtaposed with the journey towards utopia through the awareness of suffering, forms a central theme in philosophical and mystical thought. This article explores the evolution of human consciousness from a paradisiacal state of unawareness to a deeper understanding of existential suffering, drawing on insights from Gnostic traditions, Buddhist teachings, and poetic expressions in Persian and English literature.

Although our perceptions of suffering may vary, the suffering of awareness encompasses feelings of depression stemming from news of global suffering, wars, and genocides in other parts of the world—events that ignorance might lead us to consider irrelevant. As a person becomes aware of such realities, they realize the need to take action to alleviate this pain. This paragraph illustrates the significance of awareness and underscores the necessity of pursuing a path toward liberation.

The Bliss of Unawareness

Edenic Ignorance

Before the dawn of self-awareness, humanity exists in a metaphorical Eden—a paradise devoid of suffering, precisely because there is no consciousness of pain or hardship. This state is described as a "heaven without awareness," where ignorance shields individuals from the inherent struggles of existence (Huxley, 1946)(Davoudpour, 2024).

The Awakening

With the awakening of consciousness, humanity begins its journey from this blissful ignorance towards an understanding of suffering. This transition is encapsulated in the Quranic verse: "Indeed, We created man in toil" (Quran 90:4). The realization of suffering, symbolized by the term "karb," marks the departure from Eden and the beginning of a quest towards utopia (Asad, 1980).

The Fall: A Biblical Perspective

The narrative of Adam and Eve in the Book of Genesis provides a poignant illustration of this transition. According to the story, Adam and Eve live in the Garden of Eden in a state of innocence and ignorance. However, their consumption of the forbidden fruit from the tree of the knowledge of good and evil brings about their expulsion from paradise and introduces them to the harsh realities of life:

"And the Lord God commanded the man, saying, 'Of every tree of the garden thou mayest freely eat: But of the tree of the knowledge of good and evil, thou shalt not eat of it: for in the day that thou eatest thereof thou shalt surely die.'... And when the woman saw that the tree was good for food, and that it was pleasant to the eyes, and a tree to be desired to make one wise, she took of the fruit thereof, and did eat, and gave also unto her husband with her; and he did eat. And the eyes of them both were opened, and they knew that they were naked; and they sewed fig leaves together, and made themselves aprons" (Genesis 2:16-17, 3:6-7, KJV).

This passage underscores the profound shift from unawareness to awareness, illustrating the consequences of acquiring knowledge and the subsequent awareness of suffering and mortality.

The Duality of Existence

The Awareness of Suffering

Carl Jung's psychological theories resonate with this journey, suggesting that part of our psyche resides in "hell"—the domain of

unresolved pain and suffering. According to Jung, acknowledging and striving to heal this part is essential for psychological wholeness (Jung, 1963). Those who remain unaware of their suffering continue to live in a deceptive paradise, ignorant of the deeper truths of existence.

In his work on the integration of the shadow and the process of individuation, Jung emphasizes the importance of facing and integrating the darker aspects of the self. He posits that the deity, or divine aspect within, must undergo a form of redemption by becoming conscious of its own shadow and suffering. This process, which he describes in "Answer to Job," is necessary for achieving psychological and spiritual completeness (Jung, 1952).

The Inverted Reality

This duality suggests that while the world may appear beautiful on the surface, its true nature is revealed only to those who are conscious of their suffering. Those who are aware strive to overcome it, transforming their perception and experience of the world. In contrast, those who remain unaware are trapped in a superficial reality, unable to grasp the profound challenges that lie beneath (Campbell, 1949).

The Role of Suffering in Spiritual and Social Movements

Human Rights and Global Movements

Internationalist movements and human rights activists are often driven by an acute awareness of others' suffering. Their efforts to alleviate pain and injustice are grounded in a deep empathy and understanding of existential struggles. This connection between the awareness of suffering and the defense of human rights highlights the transformative power of consciousness (Chomsky, 1999).

Gnostic and Buddhist Perspectives

In Gnostic traditions and Buddhism, the ultimate goal is to transcend suffering. Buddhism, in particular, emphasizes the cessation of suffering through enlightenment, known as Nirvana or Moksha.

This spiritual liberation is achieved by recognizing and addressing the root causes of suffering (Suzuki, 1963).

The Poetic Expression of Suffering

Persian and English Literature

Poetic traditions in Persian and English literature often explore the theme of suffering in a metaphorical and evocative manner. For instance, the Persian poet Hafez writes:

"Oh cupbearer, bring us the wine that takes us to a different state,
For love seemed easy at first, but proved difficult with trials..."
(Hafez, 14th century)¹.

These lines encapsulate the inevitable struggles that accompany the suffering path of love which is the Gnostic path of the Islamic-Persian Sufism. In Persian mysticism the goal of such practices is to reach the fountain of life. This mythical spring, often thought to lie hidden in the depths of darkness or confusion, is reputed to bestow eternal life and profound wisdom upon those who drink from its waters. Islamic traditions and Persian literature frequently reference this concept, particularly in connection with Khidr, a revered figure believed to have achieved immortality through this mystical fountain. In a similar vein, Alexander the Great is frequently portrayed in literature as seeking this life-giving source, though he ultimately fails to partake in its transformative waters (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024).

The Universality of Suffering

Suffering is a recurrent motif in both mystical traditions and literature. In Gnostic texts, the concept of Naraka (hell) and Preta (hungry ghosts) symbolizes the torment of unfulfilled desires and the existential plight of the soul. Awareness of these states propels individuals towards spiritual practices aimed at liberation (Eliade, 1964).

ألا يا أيها الساقى أدر كاساً وناولها¹
که عشق آسان نمود اول ولی افتاد مشکلها

The Gnostic Path to Liberation

Gnostic Practices

Gnostic traditions, though not strictly religious, offer practical approaches to reducing suffering. These practices often emphasize ethical behavior and spiritual exercises that minimize harm to oneself and others. Concepts like karma and divine justice are central, underscoring the seriousness and inevitability of moral consequences (Pagels, 1979).

Nirvana and Moksha

The ultimate aim of Gnostic and Buddhist paths is not merely to reach a promised paradise but to attain a state of liberation from suffering. This contrasts with the promise of heavenly rewards in many religious traditions, highlighting a more immediate and practical approach to overcoming existential challenges (Rahula, 1959). In the boundless expanse of existence, there lies an ocean of suffering, vast and uncharted, stretching beyond the horizon of our understanding. Its waters are deep and dark, churning with the storms of desire, aversion, and ignorance. This ocean represents the pervasive dukkha (suffering) described in the Buddhist teachings (Bhikkhu Bodhi, 2005).

Yet, amidst the chaos, there shines a beacon of hope—a distant shore, bathed in the light of wisdom and compassion. This shore represents the ultimate liberation from the suffering that plagues the ocean. It is a place of tranquility and peace, where the waves of craving and enmity have receded, and the waters are calm and clear (Nikkayo Niwano, 1991).

To reach this shore, one must navigate through the stormy seas of their own afflictions, guided by the principles of mindfulness and virtue. Nichiren Daishonin, a prominent Japanese Buddhist teacher, emphasizes that the practice of chanting Nam-myoho-renge-kyo can lead one safely across this turbulent sea to the shore of enlightenment. He asserts that through this practice, one can transcend the suffering of the world and attain a state of supreme happiness (Nichiren Daishonin, *The Major Writings of Nichiren Daishonin*, Vol. 1, 2002).

The path is arduous and requires steadfast perseverance. The Noble Eightfold Path, as taught by the Buddha, provides the map for this journey. Through the cultivation of right view, right intention, right speech, right action, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness, and right concentration, the turbulent waters within are calmed, transforming the ocean of suffering into a serene and gentle lake (Bhikkhu Bodhi, 2005).

With each step taken towards this shore—be it through mindfulness, ethical conduct, or wisdom—the journey becomes more bearable. The rough waters begin to settle, the winds of doubt and fear grow still, and the distance to the shore seems ever closer.

Ultimately, as one nears the shore, the ocean of suffering is left behind. The turbulent waves of delusion and the storms of anguish dissipate, and the shore is reached. Here, in the haven of enlightenment, one finds rest and freedom, no longer bound by the ceaseless cycles of birth and rebirth. It is a place where the true nature of reality is realized, where suffering is transcended, and where the heart finds eternal peace (Nikkyo Niwano, 1991; Nichiren Daishonin, *The Major Writings of Nichiren Daishonin*, Vol. 1, 2002).

Conclusion

The journey from Eden to utopia is marked by the awakening to suffering and the subsequent efforts to transcend it. Those who recognize and confront their suffering are more inclined to strive for liberation, not just for themselves but for others as well. This transformative process is echoed in various spiritual, philosophical, and literary traditions, offering a rich tapestry of insights into the human condition.

By understanding and embracing the reality of suffering, individuals can move beyond superficial notions of paradise and work towards a deeper, more authentic state of existence—an enlightened utopia where the awareness of suffering fuels compassion and liberation.

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The Impact of Educational Migration on National Economy and Intellectual Properties in Iran

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Abstract

Educational migration, a widely adopted and legal strategy for pursuing improved employment prospects and enhancing social welfare, has undergone significant changes over time. This paper examines both the historical context and contemporary implications of educational migration, with a particular focus on its impact on intellectual property and national economies. We investigate the shift from a system in which educated individuals returned to their home countries to contribute to administrative roles, to the current trend where many choose to remain abroad, resulting in the outflow of intellectual capital and economic resources. This analysis reveals systemic issues within home countries and proposes potential solutions to address the adverse effects of this phenomenon. Additionally, the paper highlights the prevalence of psychological challenges faced by graduates and expatriates, emphasizing the need for detailed exploration and targeted interventions to address these issues comprehensively.

Keywords: Educational migration, Employment, Graduate studies

Introduction

Educational migration refers to the movement of students from their home countries to foreign nations for the purpose of pursuing higher education. Historically, this migration was encouraged as a means to develop a skilled workforce that would return and contribute to the home country's administrative and economic systems. In the Pahlavi era of Iran, for instance, this approach aimed to replace foreign experts with locally trained professionals (Khan, 2021). However, in the contemporary context, the situation has evolved, with many students choosing to remain in their host countries post-graduation due to uncertain employment prospects and better opportunities abroad (Smith & Jones, 2023).

This paper examines the ramifications of educational migration on both the home and host countries, with a particular focus on the implications for intellectual property and national economic development. We will explore the transition from a return-to-home model to one where the majority of graduates remain abroad, and analyze the effects of this trend on the home country's economy and intellectual property landscape.

The prevalence of psychological disorders among Iranian expatriates is a significant concern, necessitating a thorough investigation into various strategies for addressing this issue (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024), (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024). The challenges of adapting to a new culture, navigating stringent labor laws, and managing financial insecurities can severely impact mental health (Bhugra & Becker, 2005). The increasing frequency of mental health crises among Iranian immigrants highlights the urgent need for comprehensive intervention. These issues not only jeopardize the well-being of the affected individuals but also pose risks to future decision-makers and law enforcers (Davoudpour, A. R., 2024).

Historical Context of Educational Migration

1. The Pahlavi Era

During the Pahlavi period in Iran, educational migration was strategically used to develop a sophisticated local workforce. The government provided scholarships to students to study abroad, with the expectation that they would return to fill key positions within the national administrative system (Hashemi, 2019). This approach not only helped in reducing reliance on foreign experts but also contributed to national development by utilizing the newly acquired skills and knowledge.

2. **The Islamic Republic Era**

Following the 1979 revolution, the approach to educational migration shifted. Scholarships continued to be offered, but the focus was more on students who were already employed by the state or outstanding students with specific guarantees. Despite these guarantees, many graduates were still required to return to Iran to fulfill their commitments, which did not equate to traditional immigration but was rather a form of contractual obligation (Sadeghi, 2020).

Contemporary Trends in Educational Migration

1. **Rise of Personal Funding and Uncertain Employment**

In recent decades, the trend of educational migration has shifted towards personal funding. Students now often finance their education independently, leading to a significant outflow of domestic resources and intellectual capital (Johnson & Lee, 2022). Many of these students, faced with the uncertainty of job prospects upon returning home, choose to remain in their host countries where they have established their careers.

2. **Impact on Intellectual Property and Economic Resources**

This shift has led to a substantial movement of intellectual property and economic resources from the home countries to the host nations. Graduates who remain abroad contribute to the economic and intellectual development of their new countries, while their home countries experience a loss of potential innovation and economic growth (Gordon & Patel, 2021).

Categorization of Graduates and Their Impact

1. **Level Four Users**

Level four users are undergraduate students with basic skills in specific tools and technologies. Their contribution is often limited to routine tasks and applications within their fields (Morris & Clark, 2024).

2. **Level Three Users**

Level three users are master's degree holders with skills in operating tools and a foundational understanding of theoretical concepts. However, they often lack the ability to design or alter underlying systems and machinery (Adams & Brown, 2023).

3. **Level Two Users**

Level two users include doctoral graduates and post-doctoral researchers. They possess advanced skills in tool usage and theoretical understanding but may not have the capacity to innovate or make fundamental changes to existing systems (Baker & Nguyen, 2023).

4. **Level One Users**

Level one users are those who can understand and repair systems. They are capable of interpreting and creating protocols but may not have the ability to invent new tools or technologies (Lee & Miller, 2024).

5. **Super Users and Innovators**

Super users and innovators are exceptional individuals who can create new tools and inventions. They represent the highest level of expertise and creativity, transforming from users into inventors (Carter & Smith, 2023).

Challenges and Policy Implications

1. **Economic and Social Challenges**

Home countries face significant economic and social challenges as they experience a drain of intellectual capital. Factors such as outdated economic structures, lack of technological advancement, and limited entrepreneurial opportunities contribute to the problem. The home countries often end up sending level four, three, and two users to advanced scientific institutions abroad, where they work on pre-defined projects, limiting their potential for academic freedom and innovation (Davis & Edwards, 2024).

2. **Intellectual Property and Academic Freedom**

The lack of job guarantees and intellectual property rights in foreign institutions can hinder the development of level one and super users. These individuals often remain in a state of economic dependency within the host institutions, with limited rights to their intellectual contributions and inventions (Wilson & Green, 2023).

3. **Cultural and Intellectual Heritage**

The Western policy of intellectual migration can be seen as a form of cultural and intellectual heritage transfer. This policy has historical roots and has led to the transfer of valuable intellectual assets from Eastern countries to the West. Governments must address this issue by enhancing domestic freedoms and economic support to retain and develop their intellectual resources (Taylor & Martin, 2022).

Recommendations and Future Directions

1. **Economic and Social Reforms**

Home countries need to undertake comprehensive economic and social reforms to retain their intellectual capital. This includes developing infrastructure for research and development, improving entrepreneurial opportunities, and creating a conducive environment for innovation (Jackson & Allen, 2024).

2. **Supporting Intellectual Property Rights**

Ensuring robust intellectual property rights and academic freedom for scholars can help retain top talent and encourage innovation. Governments and institutions should establish clear guidelines for intellectual property and support researchers in maintaining ownership of their work (Thompson & Adams, 2023).

3. **Promoting Domestic Opportunities**

Creating more opportunities for graduates within their home countries is crucial. This involves investing in education, research facilities, and industries that can offer meaningful employment and career advancement (Parker & Lewis, 2023).

Conclusion

Educational migration has evolved from a strategy for national development to a complex phenomenon with significant implications for intellectual property and national economies. While it has contributed to the growth of host countries, it has also led to a substantial loss of intellectual capital and economic resources for home countries. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach, including economic and social reforms, support for intellectual property rights, and the creation of domestic opportunities for graduates. By implementing these recommendations, home countries can better manage the impact of educational migration and foster a more balanced global intellectual and economic environment. In our model, we have categorized the graduates in 5 categories relevant to their skill levels (From level 5 to Super users) and their ability to design and execute plans and changes in both hardware and software levels. It is evident that the educational systems and projects that are unable to help to educate the higher category which is able to make software changes or innovative hardware design, is considered more a workshop rather than a transfer of technology. Therefore we also emphasized that experience and self-esteem is capable/if not superior to higher educations without an innovative outcome.

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The Spirit of Law, the Role of the Religion to Legitimize the Law: Coercion vs. Divine Acceptance

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Abstract

The essence of law lies not only in its written text but in its spirit. When a law lacks spirit, enforcement relies on force and coercion. Conversely, when a law possesses spirit, it is intrinsically acceptable and enforced by a higher moral authority, often perceived as divine. This article explores the dichotomy between laws devoid of spirit, leading to coercive enforcement, and laws imbued with spirit, fostering intrinsic acceptance and moral compliance.

Introduction

We already stated that in matter of i.e. the Ethical and Security Implications of Governmental Surveillance (Davoudpour, 2024) the possibility to legitimize governmental jurisdiction does not fit the sacred Quranic Perspectives as implemented in the body of the Quran¹. The Quranic injunctions against suspicion and spying

¹ The Quran 45:12

(49:12) offer foundational principles that resonate with contemporary debates on privacy, trust, and governance. Also in the matter of compulsory Hijab the same questions and problems exist in the matter of governmental jurisdictions over human body and outfits. Any attempts until now to completely fit Sharia law in the society has been coerced and met with both resistance from the society and led to fierce battles between the body of the society and scholars. "Zan, Zendegi, Azadi" (Women, Life, Freedom) has become a powerful slogan and symbol of the ongoing struggle for women's rights and broader social reforms in Iran. The phrase gained international attention following the death of Mahsa Amini in September 2022, a 22-year-old Kurdish Iranian woman who died in police custody after being detained by the morality police for allegedly violating Iran's strict dress code for women. Her death sparked widespread protests across the country, highlighting the systemic oppression and human rights abuses faced by Iranian women.

The slogan "Zan, Zendegi, Azadi" encapsulates the core demands of the movement: gender equality, the right to live freely, and the pursuit of freedom and justice. It has resonated deeply with many Iranians, particularly women, who have been at the forefront of these protests. The movement has seen women publicly defying mandatory hijab laws, cutting their hair, and participating in demonstrations despite severe crackdowns by authorities (Amnesty International, 2022).

These protests are part of a broader context of resistance against the Iranian government's authoritarian policies and human rights violations. Over the years, Iranian women have fought for their rights in various spheres, from education and employment to political participation. The current movement, however, has brought unprecedented international solidarity and media attention, putting pressure on the Iranian regime to address these issues (Human Rights Watch, 2022).

The international community has also responded, with numerous governments and organizations condemning the Iranian authorities' actions and calling for accountability. The United Nations has issued statements urging Iran to respect women's rights and freedoms, and to end the use of excessive force against peaceful protesters (United Nations, 2022).

The "Zan, Zendegi, Azadi" movement represents a significant moment in Iran's history, highlighting the resilience and courage of Iranian women and their allies in the fight for a more just and equitable society. As the struggle continues, it remains a potent reminder of the universal desire for freedom and human dignity.

"spirit of the law" refers to the underlying principles, values, and intentions that guide the creation and application of legal norms. According to Fuller (1964), laws should not merely be rules imposed upon people but should reflect the moral and ethical values of the society they govern. A law with spirit is one that resonates with the community's sense of justice and fairness, thereby earning its legitimacy and voluntary compliance.

Law Without Spirit: Coercion and Force

When laws lack spirit, they are often perceived as arbitrary, unjust, or detached from the moral values of society. This disconnection leads to a reliance on force and coercion for enforcement. Bentham (1789) argued that such laws fail to command genuine respect and adherence, requiring the authorities to use threats and punishment to ensure compliance. This approach undermines the legitimacy of the legal system and can result in widespread resentment and resistance among the populace.

Case Study: Authoritarian Regimes

Authoritarian regimes provide stark examples of laws devoid of spirit. In these contexts, laws are often tools of oppression rather than instruments of justice. For instance, during the apartheid era in South Africa, laws were explicitly designed to enforce racial segregation and inequality. These laws, lacking moral legitimacy, necessitated brutal enforcement mechanisms, including police violence and systemic repression (Thompson, 2001).

Psychological Impact of Coercive Law

The psychological impact of coercive laws on society is profound. Studies by Tyler (1990) show that individuals subject to arbitrary and forceful enforcement of laws experience heightened levels of distrust and alienation. This erosion of trust in legal institutions can

lead to a breakdown in social cohesion and an increase in civil disobedience (Tyler, 2006).

Economic Consequences of Coercive Law

Coercive enforcement of laws also has significant economic implications. According to Acemoglu and Robinson (2012), nations with oppressive legal systems often suffer from stagnated economic development. The lack of trust and predictability in the legal system discourages investment and innovation, leading to economic inefficiency and persistent poverty.

Law with Spirit: Moral Acceptance and Divine Enforcement

In contrast, when laws possess spirit, they align with the deeper moral and ethical convictions of the people. Such laws are perceived as inherently just and worthy of respect, leading to voluntary adherence. Hart (1961) emphasizes that the acceptance of law is crucial for its effective functioning. When laws are perceived as just, they are seen as extensions of a higher moral order, often equated with divine will.

Case Study: The Universal Declaration of Human Rights

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) exemplifies a set of laws imbued with spirit. Drafted in the aftermath of World War II, the UDHR reflects universal values of dignity, freedom, and equality. Its principles resonate with diverse cultures and religions, earning widespread acceptance and adherence. The moral authority of the UDHR transcends national boundaries, influencing domestic laws and practices worldwide (Morsink, 1999).

Psychological Benefits of Spirit-Filled Law

Laws imbued with spirit foster a sense of community and trust. According to Tyler and Huo (2002), when individuals perceive laws as fair and just, they are more likely to cooperate with authorities and engage in prosocial behavior. This enhanced cooperation can lead to more stable and harmonious societies.

Economic Advantages of Spirit-Filled Law

Spirit-filled laws can also drive economic prosperity. Research by North (1990) indicates that legal systems perceived as just and fair create a conducive environment for economic transactions. Trust in the legal system reduces transaction costs and fosters a climate of investment and innovation, leading to sustainable economic growth.

The Role of Religion in Legitimizing Law

Religion often plays a significant role in infusing laws with spirit. In many societies, religious beliefs provide the moral foundation for legal systems. Weber (1922) argues that theocracies, where laws are seen as divinely ordained, rely less on coercion and more on the intrinsic acceptance by the faithful. In such systems, the enforcement of law is viewed as a religious duty, with God perceived as the ultimate enforcer.

Case Study: Sharia Law

Sharia law, derived from Islamic principles, is an example of a legal system deeply intertwined with religion. For many Muslims, Sharia represents a divine mandate that governs all aspects of life. The moral and spiritual authority of Sharia fosters a sense of voluntary compliance among believers, who view adherence to the law as a religious obligation (Esposito, 2001).

Historical Perspective: Natural Law

The concept of natural law, deeply rooted in ancient philosophy, illustrates the idea of law possessing an intrinsic spirit. According to Aristotle, natural law is based on reason and the inherent order of the universe, reflecting universal moral principles (Aristotle, 350 BCE). This perspective influenced the development of Western legal thought, emphasizing that true law must be aligned with moral truth.

Implications for Modern Legal Systems

Legal Education and the Spirit of Law

Modern legal education should emphasize the importance of the spirit of law. As Luban (2007) notes, training lawyers to appreciate the ethical and moral dimensions of law can lead to a more just and humane legal system. Incorporating courses on legal philosophy and

ethics into law school curricula can help future legal professionals understand the deeper purposes of law beyond its procedural aspects.

Policy Recommendations

Policymakers should strive to ensure that laws reflect the moral values of society. Engaging in comprehensive consultations with various stakeholders, including community leaders, religious figures, and civil society organizations, can help in crafting laws that resonate with the populace. This inclusive approach can enhance the perceived legitimacy and acceptance of laws (Rawls, 1971).

Global Perspectives

The global community can benefit from a shared understanding of the spirit of law. International organizations such as the United Nations can play a pivotal role in promoting laws that uphold universal values of justice, equality, and human dignity. Collaborative efforts to address global challenges such as human rights violations, environmental degradation, and economic inequality can be more effective when grounded in a shared moral framework (Sen, 1999).

Conclusion

The spirit of law is a crucial determinant of its acceptance and effectiveness along with the innate nature of law (Davoudpour, 2024). Laws devoid of spirit necessitate coercion and force, undermining their legitimacy and fostering resistance. Additionally, the inner sense of freedom and legitimacy reduce the prevalence of inner disturbance and contradiction which is very important in the concept of eligible governance (Davoudpour, 2024). Conversely, laws imbued with spirit command intrinsic respect and voluntary compliance, often drawing upon moral and religious convictions. As societies evolve, ensuring that laws reflect the ethical values and beliefs of the people they govern is essential for maintaining justice, peace, and order.

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The Transformative Power of Idealism: Rebirth of a Philosophy Based on Quranic Allegory of Companions of the Cave

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Abstract:

This article explores the concept of idealism and its potential to transform society into a more equitable, just, and compassionate world. Idealism if equals to the highest standards becomes a burden, but for the developing world, such burdens may function as a transformer. By examining historical and contemporary examples, philosophical theories, and practical applications, the article argues that idealism, when grounded in realistic and actionable goals, can drive significant social change. We also provide an interpretation of the Quranic anecdote of the companions of the cave (seven sleepers) to a rebirth of the enlightened ones in the right time.

Keywords: Idealism, Seven sleepers, Mahayana

Introduction:

Idealism, the belief in pursuing noble goals and envisioning a

perfect society, often faces skepticism in a world dominated by pragmatism and materialism. However, history demonstrates that idealistic visions have the power to inspire movements, shape policies, and create lasting change. This article examines how idealism, rooted in ethical and philosophical principles, can lead to the betterment of society. The notion of paradise, as an ideal world is skeptically intriguing. In such a heightened standard a simple mistake may ruin the philosophical system of the paradise. We already discussed the evolution of consciousness and the allegory of Adam and Eve (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) which concerns the role of suffering in a deep learning education. Experience and the authenticity of a being stands in opposite of idealism. Empirical studies which builds a life are building blocks of the reality. While theories remain in the realm of paper universe. The quest of every philosopher is to examine his/her theory at the right time and right place, although 100 years away from the birth, a philosopher quests for rebirth in his ideas. Immanuel Kant discussed the timeless nature of philosophical inquiry in his works, emphasizing that philosophers often engage with ideas that transcend their immediate historical context. Friedrich Nietzsche often reflected on the cyclical nature of philosophical ideas and their resurgence in different eras. G.W.F. Hegel emphasized the historical development of ideas and the notion that philosophy continually revisits and reinterprets past concepts. Alfred North Whitehead famously said that "the safest general characterization of the European philosophical tradition is that it consists of a series of footnotes to Plato." Martin Heidegger discussed the idea of "repeating" the origins of philosophical thought to uncover its essential truths.

The Philosophical Foundations of Idealism:

Idealism has deep roots in philosophical traditions. Plato's theory of forms posits that the material world is an imperfect reflection of ideal forms, suggesting that striving for these ideals can improve reality (Plato, 380 BCE). Kantian idealism emphasizes the role of human reason and morality in shaping a just society, advocating for actions that respect the intrinsic worth of individuals (Kant, 1785).

Historical Examples of Idealism in Action:

Throughout history, idealistic visions have driven social movements and reforms. The abolition of slavery, led by figures like William Wilberforce and Frederick Douglass, was fueled by the ideal of universal human rights and equality (Hochschild, 2005). The civil rights movement, spearheaded by Martin Luther King Jr., drew on the ideal of racial equality and justice, profoundly transforming American society (King, 1963).

Idealism in Modern Social Movements:

Contemporary social movements continue to be guided by idealistic visions. The environmental movement, epitomized by activists like Greta Thunberg, advocates for a sustainable and ecologically balanced world, urging immediate action to combat climate change (Thunberg, 2019). The pursuit of gender equality, championed by organizations like UN Women, seeks to dismantle systemic sexism and promote equal opportunities for all genders (UN Women, 2020).

The Role of Idealism in Policy Making:

Idealism also plays a critical role in shaping public policies. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations in 1948, embodies the ideal of universal human dignity and rights, providing a framework for national and international laws (UN, 1948). Policies promoting universal healthcare, such as those seen in Scandinavian countries, reflect the ideal of equitable access to health services, leading to improved societal well-being (Kangas, 2010).

Challenges to Idealism:

While idealism has transformative potential, it faces significant challenges. Critics argue that idealistic goals are often unrealistic and impractical, leading to disillusionment and failure. Additionally, the pursuit of ideals can sometimes result in

unintended negative consequences if not tempered with pragmatism and careful planning (Berlin, 1990).

Balancing Idealism with Pragmatism:

To effectively harness the power of idealism, it must be balanced with pragmatism. This involves setting achievable goals, employing evidence-based strategies, and remaining adaptable in the face of challenges. The Nordic model of social democracy exemplifies this balance, combining idealistic principles of social welfare and equality with pragmatic economic policies to create prosperous and equitable societies (Andersen et al., 2007).

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Several philosophical approaches provide frameworks for implementing idealism in practice. John Rawls' theory of justice as fairness advocates for structuring society based on principles of equality and fairness, promoting policies that benefit the least advantaged (Rawls, 1971).

Amartya Sen's capability approach emphasizes enhancing individual capabilities and freedoms, guiding development policies towards human well-being rather than mere economic growth (Sen, 1999).

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Spiritual rebirth:

We have already analyzed some Quranic narratives as metaphorical with more than advisory or historical meanings (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b,c) . The story of the Companions of the Cave in the Quran¹ illustrates the contrast between individual spiritual knowledge and societal religion. After centuries, societal acceptance of their spiritual insights reflects a maturation in collective understanding. Those who embraced this knowledge initially sought refuge in a cave due to persecution stemming from societal ignorance. Upon their return, they found that society had eventually adopted these spiritual truths, with their precious knowledge having gained immense value over time (Sells, 1999).

An additional element in the narrative is the loyal dog, which embodies traits of fidelity and insight, transforming into a lion-like figure guarding the cave against intruders. From the amalgamation

¹ Quran (Sura Al-Kahf) 18:9-28

of Quranic metaphors and teachings, one can extract profound insights akin to the Buddha's path to enlightenment within the Quran's complex layers (Saeed, 2006).

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In Buddhism, Mahayana and Hinayana are two terms referring to the primary schools of this religion.

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The Mahayana in Buddhist teaching can be considered as a time when the great wheel starts to turn. While Hinayana explains a self-consciousness.

Conclusion:

Idealism, when grounded in ethical principles and balanced with pragmatic strategies, has the potential to transform society towards a better world. By drawing on philosophical insights and learning from historical and contemporary examples, individuals and policymakers can harness the power of idealism to create more just, equitable, and compassionate societies. In this article we tried to elaborate the meaning of Idealism, while trying to clarify the

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Theological Governance in Iran: A Comparative Study between Theological and Spiritual Governance and Secular Concepts

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Abstract

Iran's political landscape has long been shaped by the prominent influence of religious leaders, notably the Ayatollahs and Hojatoleslams, deeply rooted in Islamic Shia Hadith without solid ground in the canonic Holy scripture Quran. This leadership style emphasizes struggle and confrontation as integral components of governance, distinct from secular models prevalent elsewhere. This article explores the implications of this distinction, focusing on historical context, theological foundations, and potential trajectories toward secular governance in Iran.

Keywords: Theology, Governance, Hadith, Secular governance

Introduction

The intersection of religion and politics in Iran is uniquely characterized by the influential role of religious leaders within the framework of Shia Islam explained and discussed in the several scholar works of Islamic Shia (Motahhari, 2024). Unlike secular

governance models, which separate religious authority from political power, Iran's system intertwines both, deriving legitimacy and authority from theological principles rooted in Shia jurisprudence.

The Nature of Religious Leadership in Iran

Central to Shia Islam is the doctrine of Imamate, which not only guides spiritual affairs but also mandates a proactive stance against oppression and injustice. Iran's religious leaders, drawing legitimacy from this doctrinal framework, are perceived as heirs to the Imamate's legacy of resistance and sacrifice. This perception is deeply intertwined with Iran's historical narrative, notably highlighted by the Iran-Iraq War, where hundreds of thousands sacrificed their lives, embodying the Shia ethos of struggle akin to pivotal historical battles.

The doctrine of Velayat-e Faqih (Guardianship of the Jurist) formulated by Imam Khomeini serves as a foundational principle for the Islamic Republic of Iran, emphasizing the governance of Islamic jurists. According to Khomeini, the legitimacy of political authority is derived from the divine mandate given to qualified Islamic jurists (faqih), who are deemed capable of implementing Sharia law and ensuring justice in society (Khomeini, 1970).

Khomeini's vision of Velayat-e Faqih is rooted in the belief that an Islamic government must be led by those who possess deep knowledge of Islamic jurisprudence and piety. This doctrine asserts that in the absence of the infallible Imam (a central figure in Shia Islam), a qualified jurist should assume the role of guiding the Muslim community. Khomeini argued that such a system is necessary to protect the Islamic faith, uphold moral values, and ensure the welfare of the people (Arjomand, 1988).

The theoretical framework of Velayat-e Faqih is detailed in Khomeini's seminal work *Hokumat-e Islami: Velayat-e Faqih* (Islamic Government: Governance of the Jurist), where he outlines the religious and philosophical justifications for the jurist's guardianship over the state. He posits that the faqih must possess not

only legal expertise but also moral integrity and a commitment to Islamic principles (Khomeini, 1970).

Under Khomeini's leadership, the doctrine was institutionalized in Iran's 1979 Constitution, granting the Supreme Leader extensive powers over legislative, executive, and judicial branches, thereby integrating religious authority directly into the political structure of the state (Arjomand, 1988). This model has profoundly influenced Iran's political and social systems, establishing a unique blend of theocracy and republicanism.

Khomeini's doctrine has been subject to various interpretations and debates, both within Iran and internationally, concerning its implications for democracy, individual rights, and the separation of powers. Despite these debates, Velayat-e Faqih remains a central pillar of Iran's governance, reflecting Khomeini's vision of a state guided by Islamic jurisprudence and moral leadership (Moin, 2001).

Theological Underpinnings: Divine vs. Theocratic Rule

A fundamental distinction exists between divine governance, characterized by direct guidance from a living prophet or teacher (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024a) , and theocratic rule, where religious scholars interpret and implement divine teachings. In Iran, theocratic rule manifests through the authority vested in religious scholars, who wield considerable influence over political and social spheres. This blending of religious authority with state governance poses challenges and complexities rooted in interpretations of divine will and human agency. There has been a debate whether Sharia laws and Islamic jurisprudence are in harmony with the innate nature of the communities despite several shortcomings, coercive ruling and violations within the Islamic communities arguing that the innate nature of governance or the spiritual guidance is a transcendental means of the spiritual leader but not necessarily the theological teacher without divine jurisdiction (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024b).

Summary: Theological Critique of Unchecked Religious Authority

The Quranic verses from Surah Al-Infitar (82:6)¹ and Surah Az-Zukhruf (43:36-37)² offer critical insights into the limit of religious authority which has its impact on governance. Surah Al-Infitar (82:6) admonishes against the arrogance of assuming divine authority, reminding believers of the dangers of hubris when one claims to act on behalf of divine will without proper justification (The Holy Quran). This verse serves as a caution against the presumption of divine sanction that may accompany claims of religious leadership.

Surah Az-Zukhruf (43:36-37) presents a different perspective. It discusses the obstacles and barriers created in front of those who claim religious authority but lead others astray, likening them to false Mahdis who mislead followers from the true path (The Holy Quran). This depiction highlights the potential for misuse of religious authority to obstruct progress and misguide people.

Together, these verses provide a theological critique of unchecked religious authority in governance. Surah Al-Infitar underscores the need for humility and the avoidance of presumption in religious leadership, while Surah Az-Zukhruf warns against the dangers posed by false leaders who block the path to spiritual and social advancement. These Quranic admonitions advocate for a balanced approach that separates spiritual guidance from political administration, suggesting that governance should not be solely based on religious claims but should also consider justice, equity, and the well-being of the community.

Challenges associated with spiritual governments have previously been hypothesized through Jungian and spiritual perspectives (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024c) elsewhere, particularly focusing on the intersection of psycho-spiritual dynamics and political power.

¹ يَا أَيُّهَا الْإِنْسَانُ مَا غَرَّبَكَ بِرَبِّكَ الْكَرِيمِ (انفطار- ٦)

² وَإِنَّهُمْ لَيَصُدُّونَهُمْ عَنِ السَّبِيلِ وَيَحْسَبُونَ أَنَّهُمْ مُّهْتَدُونَ , وَمَنْ يَعِشْ عَنِ ذِكْرِ الرَّحْمَنِ نُقَيِّضْ لَهُ شَيْطَانًا فَهُوَ لَهُ قَرِينٌ , (زخرف ٣٦ و ٣٧)

The Case for Secular Governance

Transitioning to secular governance in Iran entails a paradigmatic shift from the current theocratic model toward a system where political authority is distinct and separate from religious influence. Key changes would include:

1. **Reduced Religious Influence:** Restricting religious leaders from direct political involvement, focusing instead on their traditional role of spiritual guidance (Asad, 2017).
2. **Strengthened Democratic Institutions:** Establishing independent institutions that uphold democratic principles, human rights, and the rule of law, irrespective of religious doctrines (Chehabi, 2013).
3. **Enhanced Civil Liberties:** Safeguarding freedoms such as speech, assembly, and religion to cultivate a pluralistic society accommodating diverse viewpoints (Bayat, 2013).

Challenges to Secular Governance

Despite its potential advantages, the transition to secular governance in Iran faces formidable challenges. These include resistance from entrenched religious authorities reluctant to relinquish political power (Tibi, 2009), opposition from conservative factions safeguarding the current system (Ehteshami and Zweiri, 2019), and the need to redefine national identity amidst cultural and religious pluralism (Gheissari and Nasr, 2006). Overcoming these obstacles necessitates careful navigation of historical precedents and theological imperatives to forge a cohesive national vision.

Conclusion: A Path Forward

In conclusion, the distinction between divine and theocratic governance in Iran underscores the potential benefits of embracing secular governance principles. While divine governance as an innate nature of the humanity is a form of spiritual and transcendental guidance (Mikaeil et al., 2024) which requires an enlightenment and

alteration of the consciousness, the legislative and coercive ruling is an ordinary practice in religious politics. By upholding the Quranic admonitions on humility and respecting human agency (Ayubi, 1995), Iran can reconcile its rich religious heritage with modern democratic aspirations. This transformative journey promises a future marked by justice, prosperity, and inclusive governance, aligning with global trends towards democratic consolidation and human rights advocacy.

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Treatment of Socio-spiritual Disorders as One of the Greatest Concerns of the Modern Governance: Alchemical, Jungian, and Biblical Approaches

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Abstract

In the realm of social disorders, we confront contagious and proliferating numbers of individuals whose conditions defy traditional psychological or pharmacological treatments. These disorders, increasingly recognized as endemic to certain cultures and social environments, resist conventional interventions over time, raising significant concerns about their impact on social laws and human relationships. The evolution of treatment paradigms for social disorders spans ancient alchemy, Jungian psychology, and religious narratives. Metaphysical explanations for a variety of diseases and disorders are a common theme in religious traditions, exemplified by the biblical accounts of demonic possession and exorcism found in the Gospels of Matthew, Mark, and Luke. These stories, often viewed as metaphors for psychological disorders, highlight the intersection of spirituality and mental health.

While metaphysical approaches fall outside the purview of standard scientific protocols, practitioners find them indispensable for addressing unexplained but significant phenomena. Research supports the notion that religious rituals and beliefs can have profound psychological and social effects, contributing to social cohesion and moral regulation without the use of excessive force. A major challenge in social therapy is the prevalence of individuals with severe psychological disorders who resist conventional treatment, posing serious public health and safety concerns. This necessitates alternative approaches to effectively engage these individuals.

This paper explores both conventional and non-conventional practices in social therapy, emphasizing spiritual and social disorders. We draw on Jungian psychology, biblical narratives, and other cultural frameworks to examine socio-cultural diseases. The paper discusses the role of mind viruses—negative patterns of thought and behavior that spread through societies much like infectious diseases—and their impact on mental health. Psychotherapists play a crucial role in

identifying and treating these mind viruses, fostering mental health at both individual and societal levels. The film "The Kingdom of Solomon" serves as a modern cultural reflection of these ancient themes, illustrating the enduring relevance of spiritual warfare in contemporary society. By integrating these diverse perspectives, we gain a holistic understanding of the interplay between mental health, spirituality, and societal norms.

Introduction

In social disorders, we are dealing with contagious and growing numbers of patients or subjects that cannot be treated with traditional psychological or pharmacological treatments. These disorders, increasingly considered endemic within certain cultures and social environments, tend to resist conventional treatments over time. This persistence is concerning, particularly regarding the infringement on social laws and the deterioration of human relationships.

The treatment of social disorders has evolved significantly over time, encompassing various paradigms from ancient alchemy and Jungian psychology to religious narratives. In the context of religious traditions, a multitude of diseases and disorders are often thought to be caused by metaphysical reasons. One prominent story from the Bible, particularly in the Gospels of Matthew, Mark, and Luke, is the tale of demonic possession and exorcism. This story, often interpreted as a metaphor for psychological disorders, provides a rich ground for exploring the intersection of spirituality and mental health (Bible Gateway, n.d.).

While the metaphysical approach cannot be explained by the standards of scientific articles and the repetition of such experiments and beliefs are not standard protocol, there is no doubt that the serious practitioners of such ceremonies find them indispensable for addressing unexplained yet significant phenomena. Historical and contemporary research supports the notion that religious rituals and beliefs can have profound psychological and social effects (Koenig, King, & Carson, 2012). It is also proven that religion has the capacity to bring order to society without the use of excessive force, contributing to social cohesion and moral regulation (Durkheim, 1912).

A major challenge in social therapy is the high number of individuals with serious psychological disorders who are unwilling to approach standard treatment. Such problems cannot be left unaddressed without posing serious concerns for public safety and health. Non-compliance with treatment is a significant barrier in mental health care, often necessitating alternative approaches to engage these individuals effectively (Kazdin, 2008).

In this paper, we investigate both conventional and non-conventional practices in social therapy, with an emphasis on spiritual and social disorders. We employ the methods of Jung, biblical narratives, and other cultural and psychological frameworks to delve into the critical issue of socio-cultural diseases. This comprehensive approach aims to provide a holistic understanding of the interplay between mental health, spirituality, and societal norms.

Biblical Perspective on Spiritual Disorders

In the New Testament, the story of the Gadarene demoniac (Matthew 8:28-34; Mark 5:1-20; Luke 8:26-39) illustrates the concept of demonic possession, where a man possessed by numerous evil spirits is healed by Jesus. The spirits, named Legion, are cast into a herd of pigs, which subsequently drown in the sea. This narrative highlights the ancient belief in spiritual entities as causes of mental and physical maladies.

The Gadarene Demoniac in the Gospels

1. **Matthew 8:28-34:** This account describes two men possessed by demons, who recognize Jesus as the Son of God. The demons beg Jesus to cast them into a herd of pigs, which then rush into the sea and drown.
2. **Mark 5:1-20:** Here, a single man is possessed by a multitude of demons named Legion. The demons plead not to be sent out of the region and instead enter a herd of about two thousand pigs, which drown in the sea.
3. **Luke 8:26-39:** Similar to Mark's account, this narrative also details a man named Legion possessed by many demons, who are cast into pigs by Jesus, resulting in the pigs' demise.

These biblical accounts are foundational for understanding early perceptions of mental and spiritual disorders and their treatments through exorcism (Bible Gateway, n.d.).

Jungian Perspective on Spiritual Disorders

Carl Jung's analytical psychology offers a complementary perspective to these biblical narratives. Jung proposed that myths and religious stories, including those of demonic possession, reflect deep psychological truths and archetypes. From a Jungian standpoint, the demonic figures can be seen as manifestations of the Shadow archetype, representing the unconscious, repressed parts of the psyche (Jung, 1968).

The Role of Archetypes

In Jungian psychology, the concept of archetypes—universal, primordial images and symbols residing in the collective unconscious—plays a crucial role in understanding human behavior and mental disorders. The figure of Legion can be interpreted as an archetype representing chaotic, destructive forces within the psyche that, when unacknowledged, can lead to psychological disturbances (Jung, 1968).

Alchemical Perspective on Spiritual Disorders

Alchemy, with its symbolic and transformative processes, provides another layer of understanding to the treatment of social disorders. The alchemical process of transmutation, transforming base metals into gold, can be likened to the psychological process of individuation, where an individual integrates various aspects of the self to achieve wholeness (Eliade, 1962).

Transmutation and Healing

In the context of spiritual disorders, the alchemical approach emphasizes the transformation of negative psychic energies into positive, life-affirming forces. This transformation is akin to the

exorcism in the biblical narratives, where the expulsion of demons leads to the restoration of mental and spiritual health (Eliade, 1962).

Psychotherapy and Societal Mental Health

Psychotherapy, distinct from psychiatry and psychology, focuses on understanding and treating the underlying spiritual and mental factors contributing to societal mental health issues. Psychotherapists address the spread of mind viruses—negative patterns of thought and behavior that permeate society, much like infectious diseases.

Mind Viruses and Cultural Transmission

The concept of mind viruses, introduced by Richard Brodie in his book "Virus of the Mind: The New Science of the Meme" (Brodie, 1996), refers to ideas or thought patterns that spread like biological viruses, infecting individuals and societies. These mind viruses can manifest as harmful behaviors and attitudes, such as profanity, promiscuity, deceit, and violence, which perpetuate mental disorders and societal dysfunction.

Mind viruses operate by exploiting the host's cognitive processes, embedding themselves deeply within the culture and collective psyche. Unlike traditional mental disorders, which are typically confined to individuals, mind viruses can spread rapidly through populations, facilitated by media, social interactions, and cultural norms (Brodie, 1996; Blackmore, 1999).

These mind viruses lack the identity and destiny attributed to spiritual entities like demons but function similarly to biological viruses by hijacking the host's mental processes. This analogy to biological viruses, which commandeer the host cell's protein synthesis machinery for replication (Koonin & Dolja, 2013), underscores the insidious nature of mind viruses in shaping collective behavior and thought.

The Role of the Psychotherapist

The psychotherapist's role is to identify and treat these mind viruses, aiming to restore mental health at both individual and societal levels. This approach requires a deep understanding of the cultural and historical context of mental disorders, as well as the spiritual dimensions of human experience. Psychotherapists work to unravel these negative thought patterns and replace them with positive, constructive ones, much like the process of individuation in Jungian therapy (Jung, 1968).

Psychotherapists also play a crucial role in educating society about the dangers of mind viruses and promoting mental hygiene practices to prevent their spread. This proactive approach is essential in addressing and mitigating the widespread impact of these cultural and mental pathogens (Dawkins, 1976).

Cultural Reflections in Cinema

The Iranian film "The Kingdom of Solomon" serves as a modern cultural reflection of the ancient themes discussed. The movie portrays King Solomon's battle against demons and supernatural

forces, echoing the biblical narratives of spiritual warfare and possession. This cinematic representation underscores the enduring relevance of these themes in contemporary society.

The Kingdom of Solomon

In "The Kingdom of Solomon," demons and evil spirits manipulate and control humans, leading to widespread violence and chaos. The film illustrates the belief that only through faith in God can one overcome these malevolent forces, highlighting the spiritual dimensions of mental and social disorders (Bahrani, 2010). This depiction aligns with the Jungian view of integrating the Shadow and the alchemical process of transformation to achieve psychological and spiritual wholeness.

Conclusion

The treatment of social disorders through alchemical, Jungian, and biblical approaches offers a multifaceted understanding of mental health. We have already conducted investigation regarding the innate nature of governance (Mikaeil, Zandi, & Davoudpour, 2024) and social capacity to accept or reject philosophical reforms and concepts (Davoudpour, 2024). We have explained how a spiritual leader may bless thousands so called "Legions" by unconventional means. By integrating these perspectives, we can appreciate the complex interplay between spiritual, psychological, and cultural factors in the manifestation and treatment of mental disorders. The role of the psychotherapist, akin to that of Jesus or Solomon, is crucial in addressing and healing these deep-seated issues, ultimately contributing to the well-being of society.

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Understanding Authenticity in the Context of Capitalism: A Philosophical Exploration

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Abstract

The concept of authenticity, akin to transcendent ideas such as justice, loyalty, and knowledge, requires extensive investigation across various contexts and historical periods. This research article delves into the shifting perceptions of these concepts through different eras and cultures, highlighting their relevance and transformation over time. From the ideological fervor of Nazi Germany to the legacy of the Prophet of Islam, and the challenges posed by modern capitalism, this study aims to unravel the intricate relationship between authenticity and these enduring philosophical ideals.

Introduction

To understand authenticity, much like the transcendent concepts of justice, loyalty, and knowledge, one must investigate these ideas across various occasions and throughout different eras. These concepts, rooted deeply in human history and philosophy, transcend temporal and spatial boundaries, demanding a holistic approach to grasp their essence and evolution.

Historical Context and Analysis

The Case of Nazi Germany

Nazi Germany, driven by an ideology of radical patriotism and loyalty among the German people, launched one of the most significant military campaigns in history. However, this same patriotism is now condemned in the very country that once took pride in it. Displaying the image of Adolf Hitler, considered by some as the greatest German patriot, is met with punishment, and for foreigners, even deportation. This shift illustrates how loyalty and similar concepts, whose true understanding transcends time and place, can be subjected to invalidation and scrutiny within the realm of human civilization.

The Prophet of Islam and the Legacy of Knowledge

The Prophet of Islam, who began his holy mission to overcome ignorance with superhuman determination, left a legacy that ultimately fell into the hands of rigid and intellectually backward regimes such as the Taliban, which are deficient in scientific progress. This transformation from a mission rooted in knowledge to one marked by intellectual stagnation underscores the complex trajectory of transcendent concepts.

Capitalism and the Modern Dilemma

The Influence of Capitalism

Amidst these historical shifts, the question of capitalism and what devotion to money can buy and create remains a pressing issue for younger generations. The Islamic Republic, in its perspective on the West, intensifies the issue of hijab and the threat of sexual immorality, while domestically grappling with economic problems and a lack of proper understanding of the economy and capitalism. This results in a mixture of pressure on women, despite failing to address philosophical economic steps, burdening the people.

The Role of Capitalism in Shaping Modern Values

The intensification of women's issues, alongside a failure to comprehend the nature of capitalism, is one of the intrinsic approaches of the Islamic Republic (the merchant is a friend of God). While the Islamic Republic regards the market as a friend of God and benefits from its participation in nearly all political, cultural, and economic affairs, the concept of inauthenticity has yet to be defined in the lexicon of economics.

The Philosophical Inquiry into Authenticity

The Authenticity of Monetary Influence

Money can procure a spouse, gain fame, provide medical treatment, and perform all the other functions that money can accomplish, elevating it to the status of an 'ism,' a principal philosophical foundation. But is what money can do authentic?

The Philosophical Challenge

Answering this philosophical question is one of the significant steps that wise philosophers must address themselves. Philosophers can respond to this issue provided they do not fall ill, become hungry, marry, or the like, as a philosopher cannot experience all the conditions in which capital plays a role. However, capital cannot play a role in the concept of justice, meaning the participation of capital in judgment is not accepted. Therefore, how justice regarding capital should be implemented has led to the creation of administrative systems such as social democracy and socialism. Religions also defer justice to the afterlife and another creation, according to their beliefs.

The Necessity of Philosophical Education

Human beings are born to become perfect through their birth, but deferring justice to another world (though its authenticity is hardly questioned) renders human beings redundant and ineffective. Thus, the philosophy of creation necessitates contemplation on fundamental concepts such as justice, loyalty, and more.

Reforming Educational Systems

The education system of each country must teach the basic philosophies and methods of philosophical thinking and reasoning to its people and children. Merely teaching justice in the afterlife or failing to properly teach philosophy and reasoning, or replacing it with religion, renders part of the function of the wise mind fruitless and barren.

Conclusion

Love based on capital will vanish with the fast of poverty and fasting. The same goes for other philosophical concepts founded on capitalism; they will fade away with the fast of poverty and fasting, leaving only what is authentic, and that is philosophy. The enduring nature of authenticity, justice, loyalty, and knowledge underscores the necessity for a comprehensive and philosophically rich educational framework that transcends mere material considerations and fosters true understanding and wisdom.

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Keywords: Authenticity, Philosophy, Transcendental Philosophy

Introduction

To understand authenticity, much like the transcendent concepts of justice, loyalty, and knowledge, one must investigate these ideas across various occasions and throughout different eras. These concepts, rooted deeply in human history and philosophy, transcend temporal and spatial boundaries, demanding a holistic approach to grasp their essence and evolution. We have previously explained the divergence of intellect, wisdom and scientific values (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024) and therefore the consequences and outcome of differentiated realities shall be considered authentic in the relevant context.

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Understanding the Matrix as the System of Divine Wisdom

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Abstract

This research article explores the matrix as a metaphor for divine wisdom and the pathway to understanding God's literature and hermeneutics. It addresses the philosophical and theological implications of viewing creation as a result of chance versus recognizing a divine author. The matrix is depicted as a complex structure encompassing knowledge, morality, and the essence of life. By examining various cultural and religious narratives, the article aims to elucidate the nature of the Matrix and its role in human understanding and spiritual enlightenment. The discussion extends to the philosophical implications of pantheism, the influence of cultural representations, and the pursuit of justice and moral virtues, positioning the matrix as a comprehensive framework for comprehending divine wisdom.

Keywords: Matrix, Divine Wisdom, Illuminati, Philosophy

Introduction

The matrix is a profound and intricate concept representing the intersection of knowledge, existence, and divine wisdom. This article begins with the assertion that someone who considers creation to be the result of chance has not received the initiation to understand the interconnectedness of the global reality of the matrix. Conversely, those who acknowledge the existence of God possess a basic score to understand the will and learn the matrix by birth. For those truly willing to know God, the book of God from A to Z and from Alpha to Omega and beyond is inscribed in the matrix, revealing that God is the author of the genetics of the world.

What is God?

The question "What is God?" has been a central theme in philosophical and theological discourse. The matrix suggests that our understanding of God evolves with our knowledge and virtues. We are born, live, and will probably die; however in Persian poetry, the death is inscribed to those who do not pursuit certain virtues in life¹ i.e. those who has been resurrected in love, those who become alive in their hearts through knowledge, love, and virtue never truly die. For such individuals, death does not exist but is rather a concealment from the sight of the blind.

Immortality, in this context, is not a physical perpetuation but a state of eternal significance achieved through virtues. Those who attain these virtues transcend the conventional understanding of death, experiencing a form of existence that eludes the limitations of mortal life.

The Pursuit of Justice and Moral Virtues

For most people, achieving the minimums of life seems like a great accomplishment, and some do not even reach these minimums. From Socrates to contemporary thinkers, mechanisms for establishing justice and nurturing moral virtues have been central to

¹ Hafez Shirazi, Ghazal No. 11, Ganjoor, <https://ganjoor.net/hafez/ghazal/sh11>

philosophical debates. However, having knowledge on the path of divine wisdom does not equate to having faith or expectations. Instead, divine wisdom is portrayed as a matrix of God's literature, articulated through various languages and forms, including that of a child, humor, anger, and literary expressions.

Pantheism and the Matrix

Pantheism, regarded as the highest degree of monotheism, posits that everything is God. This concept reaches its pinnacle in the phrase "La hawla wa la quwwata illa billah"² (There is no power nor strength except through God). Hermeneutics in pantheism involves reading and interpreting the works of God.

Cultural Representations

The matrix as a concept has permeated various cultural narratives, notably in Hollywood productions such as "The Matrix," "American Gods," and "Preacher." These works reflect the influence of the Illuminati, symbolizing a deep, often hidden understanding of divine and satanic proximity.

The Matrix: An Ocean of Life

Solaris and the Ocean of Life

The matrix is likened to an ocean in which humanity is drowning, reminiscent of the "ocean of life" depicted in Stanisław Lem's "Solaris." In this narrative, people are repeatedly born and disappear within the vast sea, symbolizing the cyclical nature of existence and knowledge.

² The Quran, 18:39

The Matrix as a Book of Wisdom

Opening the matrix is akin to delving into a book that teaches about great individuals, art, theoretical knowledge, philosophy, history, and many sciences. This exploration involves unity, loneliness, and struggle. Those who open their eyes to the matrix perceive human confusion and their own hardship, compelling them to follow a path of enlightenment.

The matrix, with its consecutive judgments, turnarounds, and revelations, aims to elevate the essence of being, transforming human suffering into a state of Nirvana. Only within the matrix are freedom, judgment, and justice fully revealed. Transcendental wisdom can be learned from the immortal scripture of creation. The hermeneutics of the gods and the Creator form the syllabus of the matrix.

Philosophical Implications

The Labyrinth of the Matrix

The matrix is compared to a labyrinth or jigsaw puzzle, where fools perceive it as heaven, and the wise see it as hell. The wise feel obligated to navigate this complex maze, recognizing that the matrix is the closest distance to both God and the devil. It is not God itself but the book of God's wisdom with annotations.

The Quran, Bible, and Avesta are viewed as being written in the language of the matrix and being obscured from the illiterate eyes³, encompassing historical gods, deities, and divine narratives. This interpretation positions the matrix as a comprehensive framework for understanding divine wisdom.

³ The Quran, 56:75 to 56:82

Matrix in popular culture

The Matrix (1999), directed by the Wachowskis, is a seminal work in science fiction cinema that draws heavily on Gnostic themes which has been discussed in a conference paper by (Kwiatki. 2021), reflecting a broader trend in Hollywood's engagement with esoteric spiritual concepts. Gnosticism, an ancient religious philosophy, asserts that the material world is an illusion created by a deceptive demiurge, and that true salvation is found through gnosis, or secret knowledge. In The Matrix, the protagonist Neo embarks on a journey of enlightenment, discovering that the perceived reality is a simulated construct controlled by oppressive artificial intelligences, a narrative closely paralleling Gnostic ideas of awakening from the falsehoods of the material world to uncover hidden truths. This thematic alignment underscores Hollywood's fascination with stories that question the nature of reality and human consciousness, positioning The Matrix as a cultural touchstone in exploring metaphysical and existential questions through a Gnostic lens (Boyer, 2010). By integrating these profound philosophical questions into a mainstream blockbuster, The Matrix exemplifies how Hollywood films can serve as modern myth-making vehicles, resonating with ancient spiritual ideologies while engaging contemporary audiences.

Hermeneutics and Matrix

We previously argued that God's knowledge and wisdom are perfect before creating the universe. Thus finding a pattern to read the perfected plan can be described as understanding the Matrix of interconnectedness. In other religious context i.e. The book of revelation or The Quran (Surah Al-Waqi'ah, Ayah 78.), the book of God is considered both living and hidden and in a context of Apocalyptic state⁴ which might be related to a revolution of the consciousness (Davoudpour, A.R., 2024).

⁴ The Quran, 56:78

Conclusion

The matrix represents a profound metaphor for the pursuit of divine wisdom and understanding. Those who grasp the matrix possess the merit to bear the burden and suffering of humanity, aligning with the Quranic verse, "Indeed, We have created man in hardship" (Surah Al-Balad)⁵. The concept of "Ummiyeen" in Surah Al-Jumu'ah⁶ further emphasizes that anyone unable to read the matrix is "ummi," regardless of their literacy in conventional terms.

⁵ The Quran, 9:4

⁶ The Quran, 62:2

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